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In this paper, Captain J. S. Taylor describes the life and work of James Lind, Thomas Trotter and Gilbert Blane.

This review was identified in a search for historical papers on scurvy.

Although the text is available through the link above, the text is difficult to read.

This is a more easy to read version of the text. A few small errors were corrected.

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THE FOUNDERS OF NAVAL HYGIENE.
LIND, TROTTER, AND BLANE.

Then swore Lord Thomas Howard: "Fore God I am no coward;
But I can not meet them here, for my ships are out of gear,
And the half my men are sick. I must fly, but follow quick;
We are six ships of the line; can we fight with fifty-three?"
(Tennyson, Ballad of the "Revenge.")

That "Britannia rules the waves" is more than an empty boast for perfervid patriots bursting into song. King Alfred modified the shape of ships, making them longer and narrower. King John, Richard III, and Henry VII had a lively appreciation of the importance of sea power. The latter founded a navy in the modern sense, and then the nation set to work soberly not to claim, but to acquire, control of the seas by lavish contributions of men and less liberal expenditure of funds through centuries of naval warfare.

Neither the sailors of Spain, France, nor Holland were lacking in courage, but the British, besides having bulldog tenacity, splendid seamanship, and well-considered strategy, used the policy of attack even when disparity of numbers, surprise, or other conditions might have argued for parry instead of thrust. As an index of this forward spirit the impartial writer should include in British naval history the deeds of the three surgeons who built up a science of naval hygiene, just as they attribute some of Nelson's success in command to his ever-present concern for the health of his men.

Lind, Trotter, and Blane were tireless leaders in a noble cause. They struggled against stupidity, ignorance, prejudice, and indifference in high places and low, the admiralty, and the fore-castle; they had the hard task of seeking to break down immemorial custom; dared to challenge tradition; hammered at the walls of a hierarchy as soul chilling, as rigorous, as iron bound as any Brahmin caste; preached seemingly frivolous, beneficent novelties to insular conservatism that held hardship essential for hardihood.

There is little glory for the reformer on his *via dolorosa*, but these men had the resolution to bear up under the blows of opposition; there was that in their blood which healed the poisoned wounds of sneer and misrepresentation and nourished them through the wasting fever of disappointment. They were heroes. Blane, because he had tact and patience and the happy faculty of making

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a pleasing impression, enjoyed the satisfaction of seeing realized many of the reforms he advocated. From the start he had influential friends, and he seems to have been persona grata with captains, admirals, and the like. Honors came to him from the start. Lind, the pioneer, a genius for observation and deduction, died too soon to reap the fruit of his labors, and had the vexation of seeing others win rewards to which he was entitled. Trotter was certainly their equal in ability, he was witty, satirical, often bitter, and he was outspoken and fearless, a combination ill calculated to win the acquiescence of military superiors. He writes convincingly to the reader of a later century; but one can readily understand why he must often have failed to get satisfactory cooperation and help from his contemporaries. All three were eminently practical men, to whom no detail of duty was negligible or unimportant, and all three were men of culture and erudition, furnishing a splendid refutation of the idea—entertained by too many young physicians in America and in our service—that great learning, especially of the classical type, militates against practical accomplishment.

JAMES LIND, the first and most original of these worthies, was, like the other two, a native of Scotland, which supplied many a surgeon to the early army and navy, and since the days of steam seems to breed an inexhaustible supply of marine engineers. He was born in 1716 and died in 1794. In 1731 he was apprenticed to a surgeon in Edinburgh. From 1739 to 1749 he cruised in the West Indies, the Mediterranean, and off the west coast of Africa as a surgeon in the royal navy. A year before leaving the service he got his M. D. from Edinburgh; a year after he was made a fellow of the Royal College of Physicians. For 10 years he lived and practiced in Edinburgh, and it was during this period that he published his two great works, “Treatise on Scurvy” (1754),^{JL1754} subsequently translated into French, and the “Essay on Preserving the Health of Seamen in the Royal Navy” (1757),^{JL1757} which was translated in due time into French, German, and Dutch. He was an honorary member of scientific societies in Paris and Copenhagen, but from his own people received scant recognition. He died just a year before the issue of antiscorbutic rations was made obligatory. The use of tenders for the reception and outfitting of recruits, as recommended by Lind, was not begun until 1781. They were known as “slop ships.” Eleven years after his proposal to distill water aboard ship Irving, also a naval surgeon, received £5,000 from the House of Commons for devising an apparatus no better than that of Lind, who was actually put on the board to determine the propriety of the award.

In 1768 was first published an “Essay on Diseases of Europeans in Hot Climates,”^{JL1768} of which five editions were published in his life-

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time. It was translated into French and German. Meanwhile (1758), Lind had been appointed physician to the Royal Naval Hospital, established only four years before at Haslar. This was a civilian appointment, and it was not until 1805 that an order in council made service afloat a prerequisite for the position. Lind remained at Haslar 25 years, and had the pleasure of seeing his son, who had first been assistant surgeon and then assistant physician under him, appointed as his successor.

While Lind is commonly accepted as the first writer on tropical diseases he was long antedated by one George Whetstone, an Elizabethan traveler and gallant, to whom archdeacon Richard Hackl-wit, of Westminster, refers in a volume of “Voyages, Navigations, Traffiques, and Discoveries of the English Nation” (1600), stating that he had shown the work to Dr. Gilbert, Queen Elizabeth’s physician, by whom it was pronounced imperfect and defective.¹ Whatever its imperfections and defects Whetstone’s treatise, “The Curing of hot Disease incident to travellers in long and Southern Voyages,” robs Lind of the title of first writer on tropical diseases. In his discussion of tropical diseases Lind has much to say about marshes and swamps in relation to fever. A hospital for sick seamen erected in Jamaica was so commodious, useful, and grand that it was called Greenwich, after the establishment on the Thames. Unfortunately it was “near a marsh upon a most unhealthy spot of ground.” Patients sent thither acquired fevers (malarial and yellow fever), and the mortality was high even when there was no overcrowding or general contagion. The site had to be abandoned. Our author makes interesting comments on the climate of Mobile and Pensacola and their prevalent fevers, for which Peruvian “bark has been found a sovereign remedy.” The contrast between ships anchored well out and residences ashore is illustrated by the good health of the crews of the *Tartar* and *Prince Edward* and that of a British regiment which came to Pensacola in 1765 and promptly lost 120 men, while 11 out of 12 officers’ wives died. The remarks on climate and conduct are pertinent and discriminating. Excess or imprudence in eating, indiscretions of any kind, lack of cleanliness, proper exercise, and fresh air count as much as heat and tropical surroundings. The sick can always be moved with safety to a place where they will have more favorable conditions for recovery—nay, they will benefit by the change. He held that for tropical ports a sort of floating hospital is better than a building ashore. Many and well authenticated are the citations to prove that sleeping ashore at night in certain localities brings on dangerous and fatal fevers. There were eight gentlemen who went one midsummer to a certain section of Florida to solicit votes for a candidate for the general assembly of the province, and

¹ Singer, C. Jour. Roy. Naval Medical Service. Vol. II, No. 4. Dr. William Gilbert (1544–1603).
<https://doi.org/10.1136/jrnms-2-495>

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after a single night's exposure all contracted a violent intermittent fever and two of them died, one being the aspirant himself.

The chapter on dysentery and cholera morbus reveals Lind as a careful prescriber and conscientious nurse whom patients could not fail to trust. He was a believer in disinfection, and held that it was better to have the cooking on the berth deck where the men lay, as the smoke then diffused itself among them, pervaded the ship, and prevented infection. The *Edgar*, of 60 guns, while off the coast of Guinea in 1765, had many deaths aboard. A vessel in company with her had few sick and no dead owing to the galleys being located as suggested.

Bark as a prophylactic is urged by Lind, instancing the success that attended the distribution of large quantities of it by the African Company to the employees in its factory, on the coast of Guinea, for use during the rainy and sickly season. The results were excellent, provided the employees could also be persuaded to eat far less meat than they were accustomed to in England.

Lind opposed the common practice of repeatedly bleeding people in the Tropics, on the theory that it caused a renovation of the system. He thought it only weakened them.

Lind's work in connection with scurvy is a model of painstaking scholarly research. He reviews the subject from the most ancient times, adverts to the possibility of its having been known to Hippocrates, quotes Dr. Poupert's opinion that the scurvy he saw in Paris was like the Athenian plague, affirms that the first authentic account of scurvy is that of the Sieur de Joinville in his history of Louis IX. (Scurvy attacked his crusaders in Egypt, 1260.)

Scurvy was for centuries the scourge of life at sea, and almost equally fatal in prisons and in military operations ashore, especially sieges. Vasco de Gama, Jacques Cartier, Lord Anson, all voyagers and discoverers, in fact, had their undertakings as well as their lives jeopardized by a stay of a few weeks at sea. Sir Richard Hawkins, in the course of 20 years, knew 10,000 men to die of scurvy. Lord Anson, in circumnavigating the globe (1740-1744), arrived at the island of Juan Fernandez with but 214 survivors out of a crew of 506 men on his flagship *Centurion*, and the *Gloucester* had but 82 left out of the original 374. His total loss on the whole voyage amounted to four-fifths of the personnel. From Quebec to Holland, from France to Russia and Hungary, the disease prevailed in troops, even when in hospital. Lind himself saw 350 cases of scurvy in a single voyage of 10 weeks. The channel fleet, in a 10 weeks' voyage, had 2,400 cases. We shall see later, in speaking of Blane, how the affection persisted, even after the proper remedies were well known, owing to the carelessness and indifference of the Government.

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Beginning with the latter part of the sixteenth century books on the subject became increasingly numerous. Before discussing the subject himself Lind reviews them methodically, giving date of publication, title, and a few facts about the authors. Thus, Baldwin Ronsseus (1564) recommended spirits, fresh herbs, and wormwood, advising against pork and fat meats. J. Wierus (1567) prescribed cinnamon, sugar, watercress, scurvy grass, whey, milk, warm food, cheerful lodgings, and freedom from care. Solomon Albert (1593) mentions acid fruits, such as oranges, and barley gruels and exercise. Peter Forest (1595) boiled the juices of scurvy grass and brooklime with sugar, making an antiscorbutic sirup called after him and highly esteemed in the low countries. Felix Plater, writing in 1608, recommended oranges. Thomas Willis discussed the subject in 1667. In 1674 Francis de le Boe, the famous Leyden professor and the reviver of clinical medical instruction, mentioned oranges for scurvy. Dr. William Cockburn, in 1696, wrote "Sea Diseases, or a Treatise of Their Nature Causes and Cure." When Lord Berkeley commanded the fleet at Torbay, in 1695, this author prevailed on his lordship to put the sick in tents ashore. More than a hundred cases, deemed almost too ill to be removed, were established in them and put on fresh provisions, with carrots, turnips, and other greens. Marked improvement was visible in a week and all got well. In 1747 Dr. John Huxham had recommended that the 1,200 scorbutics of Admiral Martin's fleet be given a vegetable diet. Charles Bisset, in 1755, wrote a "Treatise on Scurvy, designed chiefly for the use of the British Navy." Dr. Poissonnier Deperrières (1767) wrote "Traité des Maladies des Gens de mer." Edward Ives, on his voyages to India, filled half a hogshead with orange and lemon juice and one-sixth part of rum. The mixture would keep for two years. Ives was on the *Kent*, 64 guns, in Admiral Watson's squadron, and did not lose a man. Between 1541 and 1769 upward of 80 books or papers on scurvy were published in Europe.

Lind's treatment (we see from the foregoing that he was the apostle but not the originator of the orange and lemon idea) included general hygienic measures, such as fresh air, cleanliness, exercise, tonics of bark and iron. His specific remedies were dandelion, ripe fruits (particularly plums and apples), and lime or lemon juice in Malaga wine or with barley water, combined with acid gargles and mouth washes. He gives opinions based on a host of authorities and his own judicious observations and experiments. His service in the navy afforded him unsurpassed material for the first edition of his treatise on scurvy, and in later ones he could quote what he had learned at Haslar, where he sometimes saw as many as 300 or 400 scorbutics in a day. He noted that the disease was the same in every age and country.

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It was on May 20, 1870, while at sea on the *Salisbury*, that Lind began the experiment which convinced him as to what was the best treatment to pursue. He selected 12 patients, all having approximately the same symptoms of scurvy, and all quartered in a “proper apartment for the sick in the fore hold.” The diet was the same for all—viz, for breakfast, water gruel sweetened with sugar; for dinner, fresh mutton broth or light puddings or boiled biscuit with sugar; for supper, barley and raisins, rice and currants, sago and wine.

Two men received 1 quart of cider daily.

Two men received 25 drops of elixir of vitriol t. i. d. on an empty stomach, and used a gargle for their mouths.

Two men received 2 spoonfuls of vinegar, t. i. d. on an empty stomach, and used a gargle for their mouths.

Two men received one-half pint of sea water t. i. d.

Two men received t. i. d. an electuary of garlic, mustard seed, horseradish, gum myrrh, and balsam of Peru; barley water and tamarinds to drink, with cream of tartar.

Two men received two oranges and one lemon daily (but these lasted for only six days.)

The patients receiving the oranges and lemons improved the most, and with astonishing rapidity. Those taking cider came next. The elixir of vitriol was valuable only for local treatment.

Lind claimed that he was the first person to recognize the feasibility of obtaining fresh from salt water at sea by distillation alone, and showed how easily this could be done aboard ship by utilizing, if necessary, the big coppers in which the men’s food was cooked. He gave specific directions by which eight men in distress for lack of drinking water could procure themselves a pint apiece every three hours if possessed of a 5½-gallon kettle, a tea kettle, a cask, a musket, and the means of lighting a fire. He gives 1761 as the date of his discovery, thus by 10 years antedating Irving, who was rewarded by Parliament. Dr. Poissonnier did not publish his suggestion till 1764. Francis Bacon, Lord Verulam, in his “Natural History,” speaks of the knowledge common to the ancients that salt water boiled and cooled again is more potable than if itself raw. He ascribed this to some of the salt rising to the surface as a scum and the rest going to the bottom as a sediment, “and so is rather a separation than evaporation.” Sir Richard Hawkins made use of distillation to purify sea water, and tells of having on one of his voyages produced a hogshead of water, “wholesome and nourishing”; but it was generally accepted that he had added wood ashes to the water; and various substances were used by others, notably one Captain Chapman, who wrote to Dr. Fothergill in 1759 that he had added both soap and wood ashes. In 1739 Stephen Hales, an English clergyman, proposed distillation of fresh water from sea water after

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first making it undergo putrefaction. In 1753 Mr. Joshua Appleby, a chemist of Durham, used calcined bones and lapis infernalis or silver nitrate to assist the operation, and the admiralty published the details of the process in the London Gazette of January 22, 1754, for the information of the service.

In 1768 the ship of war *Dolphin*, in her second voyage around the world, on the run between Batavia and the Cape, procured 42 gallons of fresh water from 56 gallons of sea water in 5 hours 13 minutes, at an expense of 9 pounds of wood and 69 pounds of coal, so that each man on board got a quart.

It is impossible to read his "Essay on the most effective means of preserving the health of seamen in the Royal Navy" without conceiving the most profound admiration for the author's discernment and good sense. To appreciate his reserve and moderation one must acquire from other books an adequate picture of the life and practices on a man-of-war in the first half of the eighteenth century. This is vividly depicted by John Masefield in his charming *Sea Life in Nelson's Time*, which prepares one for Trotter's constant ferment and ebullition over things as he found them.

One feels in running through the writings of Lind, Trotter, and Blane that Lind was almost overwhelmed by the situation confronting him. He sees remedies and urges improvements, but he lived in surroundings that had scarcely bettered, hygienically speaking, since the days of the Tudors. Trotter, a man of very different temperament, witnessed minor reforms, and was like a combatant who at the critical moment senses the possibility of success and the necessity of immediate and supreme exertions. Blane, imperturbable, calm, reassured by the evidence of distinct progress, personally favored by fortune, takes a cheerful view and avoids altercation. But he writes well, writes nobly, has the philosophic spirit, an eminently rational viewpoint. We can believe that his success was not all the result of useful introductions to influential people, affable manners, and a guarded tongue. He had talent and poise and fully deserved his conspicuous success. Both Trotter and Blane pay homage to Lind. Trotter, though frankly disagreeing with him in many particulars, especially as regards fumigations, is outspoken in his praise and calls him the "father of nautical medicine," and many of his general hygienic suggestions are but an elaboration of those made by Lind, who blazed the way for all that has been done subsequent to his day in the British Navy and in ours.

While Lind was a believer in drugs and Trotter distinctly iconoclastic and skeptical, the former also grasped in a masterly manner the importance of regimen and of general and specific measures for the preservation of health. He speaks of "the preposterous custom

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of washing the decks after sunset,” when, of course, they must remain wet throughout the night, and washing down was the fatal hobby of British commanders. In wet weather decks should be swept and scraped, not washed, and fires should be lit to dry them out. We can imagine how willing captains were to flood the living spaces with streams of water, but to have fires in braziers disposed about the decks and to lower hot coals into holds was a bother and, of course, a menace to the safety of wooden vessels carrying ammunition.

We are still struggling feebly with the problem of moisture, largely reduced now by our heating system and electric blowers, but what must it have been in the days of wooden ships, whose massive timbers underwent prolonged “pickling” to prevent rot (the process really favored it immensely), while certain portions were steeped and boiled to permit their being curved according to the builder’s design. These vessels when launched were actually water-soaked and moldy, and decay from moisture proceeded so rapidly that a man-of-war rarely lasted more than seven or eight years unless completely overhauled and repaired at prodigious expense. Ships were rotten from the start, and sometimes decay was fully manifest even in a year or two. Lind must have had all this in mind when he declared that the dampness of ships’ timbers, a great cause of sickness, ought to be attended to when a ship was being constructed. But British naval architecture was a hidebound art, its products in every way inferior to the French ships, which sailed and handled better and would have vanquished their rivals had the gunnery and personnel been on a par with design and workmanship. With such a start we have only to add constant flushing of docks, always awash from leaky gun ports when underweigh, unpumped bilges, reeking holds, and between-deck spaces congested with dirty, sweating, ill-fed sailors, collected from still more ill-favored merchant ships, from jails, and city slums (the navy took any and everybody, refusing nothing), to produce an indescribable, almost unthinkable situation. No wonder that Lind pronounced Dr. Stephen Hales’s ventilation (a system of air pumps and windmills elaborated in 1753) “the most beneficial invention for mariners which this age has produced.”

“Nothing, I fear, has contributed more to the great sickness of late in our fleet than too strict attachment to old regulations and customs,” says Lind, with a moderation utterly beyond Trotter, and yet not savoring of the urbane diplomacy of Blane. But he makes bold to assert that the rank of the captain and the character of the ship (size and number of guns, etc.) are not the principal things to be thought of in preparing for important and distant service. This was splendidly illustrated by the voyages of Cook and Anson. The former exercised admirable foresight in the matter of personnel, equipment, and stores; the latter put to sea with a crew of convales-

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cents and Chelsea pensioners. The essential is a seasoned crew and attention to cleanliness, exercise, food, and ventilation. Lind has much to say about diet, and urges fresh provisions and fresh bread. “Fermented Bread too, from its being sooner subdued, and assimilated into Nourishment by the weakened digestive Powers, as well as on account of the Inability of Scorbutics to chew a harder Substance, might be very advantageously allowed the Sick. Nor could the Quantity consumed by them, though daily made aboard, be any Inconvenience to the necessary Oeconomy and Business of the Ship.” The ship’s biscuit was not popular. It was made in round pieces, with a hole in the middle, weighed 4 ounces, and was composed of mixed wheat and pea flour, the latter usually working itself into lumps too hard to be bitten through until age and dampness had come to the rescue. Sailors constantly threw their biscuit away, which may account for the expression “as far as you could toss a biscuit” to measure distance ! Lind wrote an essay on feeding, and was eager to find a concentrated and nutritious substance available for the sick. He recommended using 1 ounce of powdered salep (the flour made from grinding certain orchidaceous tubers), 1 ounce of portable soup, and 2 quarts of boiling water, which yielded a palatable jelly sufficient to sustain a man for a day.

He calls attention to the allowance for the sick in French men-of-war: “They carry out fowls of all sorts, bullocks, sheep, kids, eggs, etc., which are distributed to the patients according to the direction of the surgeon.” In the British service such things were for the officers only, begged of them or voluntarily contributed when some crisis made the need of delicacies peculiarly conspicuous. In Nelson’s time and before, live stock was carried on many men-of-war, the pens for sheep and cattle being located in the waist of the ships on the main deck of first raters, or the upper deck of second and third raters under the boom of the foremast, forward of the wardroom. Nautical history abounds with references to the generosity of the British officers toward the sick and wounded, but Lind and his followers wanted systematic provision by Government substituted for individual philanthropy and chance charity. Lind urged the carrying of greens, pot herbs, and vegetables, and tells in detail how they can be preserved for a reasonable time and how successful he was along this line.

First, he takes up the prevention of the breeding of sickness and then discusses how its spread may be checked. Our own “health record” is foreshadowed in Lind’s insistence on careful scrutiny of the recruit. “In the usual descriptions of impressed men taken by the regulating captains it would be proper to insert their former way of life, the place of their late residence, their present state of health, and with regard to sailors [as compared to landmen] the length and

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healthfulness of their last voyage.” He realized the susceptibility of untrained men to disease, and indeed it must have required far more seasoning to accustom the landsman to the hard life of the sea in those days than now. As to landsmen, our three worthies all recognized that they were the surest victims of contagion and the great menace to the health of personnel. Lind speaks of the guard ship as often a perfect “seminary of infection to the whole fleet. I have known a thousand men confined together in one guard ship, some hundreds of whom had neither a bed nor so much as a change of linen. I have seen many of these brought into Haslar Hospital in the same clothes and shirts they had on when pressed several months before.”

Our detention and isolation methods in 1917 and 1918 would have been in operation from the creation of our Navy if our medical officers, like our predecessors in the parent establishment, had not been always hampered and circumvented by so-called “military necessity,” which, as often used, becomes the most outrageously superficial, self-contradictory phrase in the vocabulary of authority. Lind recommended a tender in the river for the detention of “the most ragged and suspicious persons, whether pressed at sea or on shore,” for at least 14 days, when “Their old Cloaths might be destroyed and new ones given them and their Persons well purified and cleaned.”

On the guard ship, fully as much as in the cruising vessel, cleanliness was the great essential. The men ought to be sent on deck with their hammocks every morning, while below all gun and air ports were opened up. At least once a month their hammocks ought to be scrubbed. He condemns the universal practice of overcrowding (a word most familiar to one who has had to read our sanitary reports for three years past). The reader will realize what the overcrowding of those days was when he recalls that a ship of 2,000 to 2,600 tons, 180 feet long at the lower gun deck level, carried from 800 to 950 men. Third raters of 1,300 to 2,000 tons and 160 feet long carried from 500 to 700 men. It took eight men to handle each one of the 40 to 75 guns and four to each carronade, and an excess of men was needed on long voyages as a *military necessity* for anticipated loss from the mortality due to disease. The overcrowding provided for the mortality in more senses than one !

Lind was a great believer in the value of exercise as a preventive of disease, and urged cold baths to increase vigor and resistance. Another preventive measure recommended is a supply of cinchona (our three writers call it bark) to ships going to fever-infested localities. Two doses daily are advised, particularly for sentries, working parties, and others on duty ashore.

Allusion has already been made to distillation. Lind told how to make filters, emphasizing the necessity of frequently changing the

sand, etc., and described minutely the familiar double-barrel arrangement.

For preventing the spread of infection, fresh air and avoidance of overcrowding are essential. The location of the sick berth is discussed at length. For infectious cases the fore-castle was preferable to holds and gun decks, as they would be away from the rest of the ship's company. In the fore-castle canvas and boards were to be used to shelter the sick from rain and wind. If the number of infectious cases or the requirements of working the ship made the fore-castle unsuitable, then they were to be installed in the gun room, even at the cost of some inconvenience to the officers who ate and slept there. The gun ports were to be kept open, and there was no real danger to the denizens of that compartment if it was kept sweet and clean. It was an accessible locality, readily cleaned up when the emergency was passed. In case permission to use the gun room was refused, the usual sick berth would be utilized; but then air holes or scuttles must be cut in each side and ventilator pipes installed for use when the weather forbade opening the scuttles. The directions to keep the sick quarters of contagious cases "free from all Incumbrances of Chests and the like; as also from Crowds of People" sounds very modern, and likewise the insistence on careful daily cleansing of all utensils, buckets, etc. We are only beginning to discard the fumigations which Lind esteemed so vital. He used vinegar, burning tar, pitch, niter, and gunpowder (for the sulphur). The clothes of the patients are to be washed and fumigated. Their linen is to be changed frequently when they sweat excessively. As soon as a bed is vacated it must be sunned, aired, fumigated, and then beat by the sick man's messmates. The sick must be set at a convenient distance from each other and not crowded, and the infected must be separated from the noninfected. The surgeons visiting a contagious case must wear "a Suite of Cloaths reserved for the purpose," linen garments, "especially waxed ones," being superior to woolen ones. Nurses and attendants on such cases should wear painted canvas jackets that can be easily washed off. After removal of the sick and their effects (as on transfer to hospital), all bulkheads are to be washed, using a good stream from a pump, so that cracks and crevices will be mechanically freed of all accretions. Then everything is to be closed up and sulphur (gunpowder) in saucers (surrounded by water) of live coals burned for two hours. The supply nearest the passage of exit is the last to be lit. After two hours everything is opened up, and by springs on the cables the hawse holes are brought into the wind so as to get a good current of air pouring through the ship.

There is need of a recovery place or berth for convalescents, but they should not be admitted to it until they have been bathed and outfitted afresh and their clothes and bedding disinfected. Finally,

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thought should be given to the influence of depressing emotions and the importance of keeping up the spirits of the infected. Remove the dead quietly and privately to a convenient place. Have persons of cheerful dispositions in attendance on patients. Furnish them amusement. Indeed, officers of the ship should enjoin and promote amusement for all sick persons.²

The greatest caution must be observed in receiving men from other ships, and when patients are transferred to a hospital the captain or surgeon should acquaint the hospital officials with the nature of their diseases previous to landing them, so they may be assigned to proper and distinct wards; otherwise they may not be distributed as their cases demand, and simply be sent to wards where there are vacant beds, without information until the surgeon receives the hospital tickets. Hospitals should have separate wards for different types of disease.

In time of war officers in guard ships must be particularly careful about the cleanliness of the ship. "Raw sailors and unseasoned marines are often the occasion of great sickness in fleets." Lind made a strong appeal for a uniform style of dress and regular issue to the recruit. This would permit the discarding or destruction of dirty and infected clothing and contribute in many ways to health and morale. (Suggested in 1774 and adopted in 1857.) Until the middle of the nineteenth century the British tar dressed pretty much as he pleased. Up to and after Nelson any filthy rag would serve as covering when he was at work aboard ship, but for liberty and parade he was very particular about his appearance, and individual taste was unrestricted. A cue was commonly worn in imitation of the marines or, perhaps, of the French sailors, but many affected curls falling to shoulders. A jacket of blue was fairly universal, and it was always bedecked with buttons and ribbons. The sailor delighted in rings, chains, earrings, charms, and furbelows of little value, bought at a fancy price from Jewish tradesmen and the bumboatmen that fed on Jack's purse in port. Trousers were wide and full, usually white, but old engravings and colored prints show that a fondness for striped trousers was quite general. Some men wore knee breeches and stockings, the latter, of course, of silk; and the low-quarter shoes had silver buckles. The greatest diversity prevailed, too, in the costume of officers. Their blue coat and white trousers are said to have been imposed by George II, who had conceived a great admiration for a certain dress, in which these colors prevailed, worn by the Duchess of Bedford. According to one authority, surgeons did not wear a distinctly naval dress until 1805. Uniform apparel for officers was not general before 1825.

2. It was Lord Nelson who introduced ship theatricals.

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Lind was plodding, painstaking, methodical, precise. His directions are clear, concise, and minute. "If any should think that the many Precautions I have mentioned are trifling, it is for fear they may be thought so, that they are so particularly inculcated." He credits to every source the ideas not original with himself and shows a wide acquaintance with everything written on the subjects he discusses and that he is fully abreast of the latest devices and practices ashore. He must have been careful in little things to be able to carry unbroken for 14 years a single Fahrenheit thermometer, taking temperature observations everywhere. There is feeling and candor, but no visible acrimony, and not a word too much in his claims to priority or originality in various schemes, and in his comments on the rewards that went to less deserving people who had better opportunities to attract the favorable notice of parliaments, councils, and committees.

In discussing asphyxiation he gives a brief suggestion for artificial respiration: "meanwhile another Person by a gentle alternate Pressure and Dilatation of the Ribs with a corresponding alternate compression of the contents of the Belly upwards imitates as near as possible the Act of Respiration in a living Body." The bulk of the treatment of the apparently drowned relates to drying and warming the body, etc., and the practice, so popular in the eighteenth century, of using rectal insufflations of tobacco smoke is not forgotten. In discussing the danger of being struck by lightning and the treatment he hazards the guess that "Experience may evince the Utility of having proper Conductors fixed at the Masthead or in the Shrouds. Meanwhile it is advisable for the Preservation of the Men who are exposed to it upon Deck, that, during violent Thunder and Lightning, the Officer take the first Opportunity of a heavy Rain falling, to employ them in some Ship-duty, with a View that their Cloaths may become wet. If this cannot be complied with, let some Artifice be fallen upon, that at least the Hats of all the Men in the Watch be dipped in Water. This may be effected in way of Play, or Diversion, among the People, without their knowing the Reason of it."

THOMAS TROTTER was born at Melrose, Scotland, in 1760 or 1761; went to school at Kelso; studied medicine at Edinburgh; and was appointed surgeon's mate to the *Berwick* in 1779. The following year found him cruising in the West Indies, and he acquired a practical knowledge of the Tropics by coming down with fever and losing all his medical stores in a hurricane. He was present during the naval engagement off Dogger Bank in 1781, and by his attention to the wounded earned the public thanks of Commodore Stewart. Promotion to surgeon came in 1782 but, a year later, following the cessation of hostilities, there was a great reduction of navy personnel, and Trotter found himself unemployed. Only 120 out of 750 surgeons

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were granted a small half pay, so he went to sea on the *Brooks*, out of Liverpool, a slaver in the West African trade. No attention was paid to his advice that the owners lay in a good supply of fresh vegetables, and the crew and cargo suffered severely from scurvy. Forty slaves died on the run to Jamaica, but the survivors brought enough to make the expedition profitable. Trotter himself was ill from fever, and on getting back to England he left the slaver, thoroughly disgusted with all he had seen and experienced. Trotter now spent five years ashore, writing, studying, and practicing his profession, and received his M. D. from Edinburgh, the subject of his thesis being "Concerning Drunkenness."

In 1789 he was appointed medical officer to the *Barfleur*, Admiral Roddam's flagship. Later he was a year at Haslar Hospital, and in 1794 was chosen fleet physician to the channel fleet under Lord Howe. In 1795 he was rendered unfit for sea service, due to a rupture contracted in going up the ship's side on a professional visit to a wounded officer, and his retirement followed in 1802. After 25 years of private practice in Newcastle, Trotter went to Edinburgh and to Roxburghshire, and finally returned to Newcastle, where he died in 1832. Trotter was a voluminous writer and did not restrict himself entirely to professional subjects, being the author of verses, a tragedy in five acts, etc. His life was one of ceaseless activity, and his outspoken conduct of a long campaign for reforms in the naval service inevitably procured him enemies. With his service colleagues he was popular, as he agitated for betterment of their condition in the matter of rank and pay, consulted them, quoted their opinions, and spoke in praise of their work. He urged Government recognition of Jenner, whom he greatly admired. In 1797, 15 surgeons in the fleet at the Cape of Good Hope joined in presenting him with a gold snuffbox "in gratitude for long and unwearied exertions" on their behalf; and in 1802 he received an urn bearing a suitable inscription, a pledge of the affection and respect of 60 medical officers regretful of his retirement from active service. Toward Blane, his superior in rank, Trotter appears to have entertained some animosity, not surprising in view of certain circumstances. Blane had begun his career at sea in a civilian capacity, been made physician to a fleet without holding any preliminary subordinate positions, and was made a commissioner on the Board for Sick and Wounded Seamen 21 years after retirement from the Navy. Trotter praises Lind in the highest terms, but disagreed with some of his teachings, and said so in unvarnished language.

Trotter's style is vigorous and pointed, but lacks the elegance and simple charm of Blane's writings. He abounds in quotations from classic authors, from Virgil to Shakespeare, and freely cites his contemporaries, including the physicians of America, among

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whom was Benjamin Rush, whom he calls the American Sydenham and greatly venerates.

His most valued works are: “A Review of the Medical Department of the British Navy with a Method of Relief Proposed” (1790); “Remarks on Naval Hospitals and Sick Quarters, with Hints for their Improvement” (1795); “The Practicable Plan for Manning the Royal Navy and Preserving Our Maritime Supremacy without Impressment” (1819),^{TT1819} which gives, incidentally, a description of one of the several mutinies of this period arising out of need for better food and pay; “Medicina Nautica” (1791-1803).^{TT1791}

The “Medicina Nautica” is of extreme interest, partly because it portrays the author as no other man could do it with pen or pencil. Like Lind and Blane, he cites a multitude of cases from his own experience and that of others, but, unlike them, he makes no scruple to say what he thinks, whether supported by the authorities or running counter to those of his time. He was a fearless critic of government and admiralty. He did not believe in disinfecting ships with vinegar or nitrous acid or any chemical for every infection that came along, and scorned to do anything as a mere placebo or for the impression it would make on the ignorant. He classes the “vinegar of the four thieves” with charms and amulets, and puts his faith in fresh air; scrupulous cleanliness; sunlight; scalding water for fomites and for bulkheads, which should be whitewashed too; prompt changes of linen and bedding; dry decks; well-ventilated decks and wards; prompt isolation and quarantine. Mattresses on shipboard ought to be covered with leather or painted canvas, so that they would not be absorptive and damp, but readily cleaned. Patients and others should be kept warm and well nourished.

The way to remove contagion from a ship is to take away the infected patient. There should be fires on the decks to overcome dampness. Overexertion and intemperance are to be avoided. Patients should be amused and the spirits of the personnel kept up. He urges supplying ships with bands and encouraging the men to dance in the evening. He himself acknowledged a passionate fondness for both music and dancing. He resents the fact that a regiment of soldiers has a band, a ship’s company none; indeed, his writings give frequent evidences of a sort of envy of the sister service. Hospitals and ships should have a system of ventilation. Burning vinegar and niter only gives a false sense of confidence and makes people forget the simpler but more important details, light, air, and soap. He repeatedly urged that soap be issued to the men, and suggests following the example of the Portuguese, who used a good salt-water soap. His general directions for the routine at Haslar could scarcely be improved on,

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and he was ambitious for the institution; wanted a good medical library there for use of doctors on visiting ships, as well as for the staff; gardens and orchards; a suitable installation for hydrotherapy. “How grateful is a Dish of Sallad after a long Cruize? How delicious an Apple, a Pear or a Plumb, after a long Sickness on Board?” He says of bathing: “Tubs were employed for this purpose while I belonged to Haslar in the form of those used in slop ships for purifying new-raised men, but the seamen had such a dislike to them that it was found impracticable to get a rheumatic patient to bathe because they reminded them of scrubbing, by way of punishment, on board. Instruments of this kind degrade a public charity: a sailor under disease ought to be bathed like a gentleman.”

His analysis of the sailor deserves to be quoted in full, but space forbids: “A Fullbred seaman is seldom a profligate character; his vices, if he has any, rarely partake of premediated villany or turpitude of conduct but rather originate, from want of reflection and a narrow understanding. Hence he plays the rogue with an awkward grace, though the degree of cunning which he occasionally practices towards his creditors bespeaks art; but from them he has learned the way to over-reach; and it ought to be remembered that they have a particular interest in emptying his pocket as quickly as possible; for his bargains with the world are limited to his landlord and slop-seller... he acquires no experience from past misfortunes and is heedless of futurity. His conversation commonly turns upon his own profession and his animadversions are almost confined to a ship, her various properties such as sailing, rigging, etc. yet the sailor has a wit of his own and he translates all occurrences into his own phrase: *Conns* a horse when he rides; *heaves the lead* from the top of a stage coach.

“Their pride consists in being reputed a thorough bred seaman, and they look upon all landsmen, as beings of inferior order. This is marked in a singular manner, by applying the language of seamanship to every transaction of life, and sometimes with a pedantic ostentation. Having little intercourse with the world, they are easily defrauded, and dupes to the deceitful, wherever they go; their money is lavished with the most thoughtless profusion; fine cloathes for his girl, a silver watch, and silver buckles for himself, are often the sole return for years of labour and hardship. When his officer happens to refuse him leave to go on shore, his purse is, sometimes, with the coldest indifference consigned to the deep, that it may no longer remind him of pleasures he cannot command.”

Impressment has a bad effect on his character, making him sullen, and he is always eager to escape: “It is also the source of numerous deceptions by making him assume diseases to be an object of invaliding. Hence he employs caustics to produce ulcers, inflates the

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urethra to give the scrotum the appearance of hernia; and drinks a decoction of tobacco to bring on emaciation, sickness at stomach and quick pulse.” But Trotter appreciates the tar’s many good features. Of his generosity he says: “His bounty is not prefaced by a common, though affected harangue, of assuring his friend that he will divide with him his last guinea: he gives the whole; requires no security, and cheerfully returns to a laborious and hazardous employment for his own support. Was I ever to be reduced to the utmost poverty, I would shun the cold threshold of fashionable charity, to beg among seamen; where my afflictions would never be insulted, by being asked, through what follies or misfortunes I had been reduced to penury.”

On the cherished British institution *impressment* our brave author remarks: “A country, that boasts so justly of her *civil rights*, ought long ago to have rescued from an involuntary engagement, a description of people, to whom she owes her greatness in the *scale* of empire. I am afraid that men high in office, have a very limited idea of the afflictions occasioned by impressing seamen. Instead of calling it, a necessary and politic measure, for the safety of the country. I pronounce it to be a most fatal and impolitic practice. It is the cause of more destruction to the health and lives of our seamen, than all other causes put together; and every nerve of invention ought to be strained, to put a speedy and effectual check to it.” The system of “requisitioning or draughting seamen and landsmen for the Navy” temporarily put into effect by an Act of Parliament under Pitt in 1795 worked admirably and Trotter thinks the liberal bounties paid were a good investment.

“In the beginning of a war, if we suppose the peace establishment to be twenty thousand men; sixty thousand more may be raised by requisition, in the like manner, and in the space of four months; by which means, seventy sail of the line, with a proportion of smaller vessels, would be ready to strike a blow before any enemy could be prepared to face us.

“The evils of impressing are manifold: a great number of our best seamen immediately disappear at the beginning of a war, and conceal themselves. It requires some time to get ships and tenders ready; the people are crowded together; they sleep on the decks; they are without cloaths to shift themselves; persons of all denominations are huddled together in a small room, and the first twelve months of a war afford a mournful task for the medical register, in the spreading of infections, and sickly crews. I fence a new commissioned fleet of ships can never be deemed an effective force at the early commencement of hostilities.”

Blane and Lind appear to have realized the evils of impressment, but the former was perhaps too closely associated with the powers

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that be, too circumspect, to speak out, and he had his own way of seeking to correct abuses.

“A general uniform for seamen has been mentioned in the valuable works of Lind and Blane, and supported by arguments so conclusive, that nothing can be offered against them. Amidst so many improvements in the navy, we are surprised that such a one as this has never been brought into universal practice... The Hon. Captain George Berkeley, when he commanded the *Magnificent*, as a guardship at Portsmouth, had his men dressed in a particular way: they were easily distinguished from others, and became proverbial for neatness of appearance, and orderly behaviour when on shore.”³

“It appears to me, that desertion would be very much prevented by it: at least, it would increase the difficulty of escape, as disguise could not be so easily assumed. The cloathes might be manufactured of a particular kind of cloth; and an act of parliament passed, enforcing the same regulations and penalties as are usual in the army.” This is followed by minute particulars of the style and amount of clothing to be issued or required. It was not until 1857 that a uniform costume was established by regulation.

Trotter was outspoken and insistent in his efforts to promote the status of the naval surgeon, and the second and larger edition of his “*Medicina Nautica*” contains his letter on the subject to Admiral Earl St. Vincent when he became first lord of the admiralty. It is a remarkable document. The medical officers of the army had recently received increase of pay and the army hospitals had been greatly improved.

“The question now turns; are the physicians and surgeons of the navy to be still doomed to poverty and neglect, amidst such unanimous and generous national favours to the army? No advocate within the walls of either House of Parliament has yet stood up to say, that the Physicians of the Royal Navy have no adequate establishment; that one half of the navy surgeons have no half pay at all; and that those who receive it, are scarcely allowed one half of the sum given to the army staff. Under such afflicting circumstances, and such apparent partiality, they must naturally look to an officer at the head of the Admiralty, who knows their value, and can feel for their situation. If you, my Lord, should treat the cause with indifference it must be abandoned as desperate.”

“Taking the surgeons on the navy list collectively, they may be justly compared to any other body of professional men; some very

3. When Lord Anson during his voyage around the world went up to Canton to visit the viceroy he put the 18 men and the coxswain of his boat in a costume resembling that of the watermen of the Thames. They wore scarlet jackets and blue silk waistcoats, liberally adorned with silver buttons, and had silver badges on jacket and cap.— Ed.

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capable, and others perhaps not. There are many of the number ably qualified for the duties of the station; liberally educated, and equal to the exercise of the art in any situation. But men thus duly informed cannot be thought to consider themselves bound to a department of public service, that affords them only a slender present support, and holds out no provision for the infirmities of age. Hence the best qualified surgeon will be the first to quit the navy when opportunity offers, and look to private life for the reward of his talents and industry. Poverty alone can confine him to a sea-life. I believe this fact is daily exemplified among us; and we are only surprised that it does not happen more frequently.

“It is one of those singular but odious customs, which we often meet with in old establishments, that a private individual should furnish, out of his emoluments of pay, the articles wanted for public service... In order to connect this business with naval forms, and to expedite service, I propose that dispensaries, or storehouses, shall be opened at the naval sea-ports, to supply ships with these articles when wanted; to be demanded by the surgeon, under the authority of his captain, in the usual manner. Four general dispensaries would be required for this business, under the direction of a surgeon who has served ten years in the navy, with a salary of 200 l. *per ann.* and house-rent. These dispensaries shall be at London, Chatham, Portsmouth and Plymouth. Ships on foreign stations shall be supplied at all places where naval stores are kept, under the care of a mate or surgeon of the list, with a suitable salary.”

It was a real hardship to receive one's salary at irregular intervals or only at the end of a cruise. “Few if any men, after an expensive education, can afford to support themselves till the ship is paid off, sometimes not for many years when employed in a foreign station.” Trotter urged quarterly payments of salaries. Once the officers have been put on a proper basis of remuneration the Government would have a right to require efficient service.

“The medical establishment being thus completed, and suitable encouragement given, government will have a right to prescribe forms of study for naval surgeons, which can alone secure persons duly qualified for the office. A term of study, which comprizes in two years two courses of lectures, on anatomy and surgery, medicine and chemistry, with at least six months' attendance at some reputable public hospital, would be requisite; exclusive of the usual apprenticeship as apothecary, which shall not be less than two years. Undeniable certificates shall be produced of these forms of education, for every one who is candidate for a surgeon's warrant. Mates of the second class and under may be admitted on easier terms.”

The old and very marked distinction between physicians and surgeons still prevailed at this time, the former being superior in edu-

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cation and standing.” No surgeon shall be promoted to the rank of physician under five years service as surgeon and mate; and their degrees as Doctors of Medicine shall be obtained in a regular manner from the Universities where they have studied the usual terms.”

Trotter calls attention to the fact that in the whole navy there were but three physicians holding naval appointments as such who had obtained their degrees in proper fashion, he being one of them. “All the others including the whole Commissioners of Sick and Hurt, have been obtained by *proxy* elsewhere ! Such is the state of medical honours in the Royal Navy of Great Britain, at the close of a nine years’ war, and at the beginning of the nineteenth century !” Rolleston doubtless rightly sees in this a slap at Blane.

Trotter was opposed to naval men engaging in private practice, and this, allowed in 1795, forbidden in 1802, was finally authorized as being of distinct advantage in 1913.

“I would also recommend two inspectors of health, to correspond with the Admiralty only; to be constantly in motion, and to inspect all hospitals, guardships, slop-ships, convalescent ships, prisons, and prison-ships, ships fitted for carrying troops, tenders, and all the private sick quarters over Great Britain and Ireland. They should watch and regulate the internal economy of health in all these, and make occasional representations to their Lordships.”

“Just as this work was going to the press, the news-papers give the account of some additional half-pay to naval officers. But it does not appear that a single word has been said of physicians, surgeons, or surgeons’ mates. We are indeed an unfriended part of the community ! Mr. Addington, himself the son of a physician, even speaks of the surgeons to look for bread from the merchant-service, as merchant ships are now to carry surgeons. But surely the nation ought to reward its own servants. Let me bring the business a little nearer to the Minister’s feedings. Would this accomplished Statesman, the conciliator of party, unassuming as he is at the head of the Treasury, would he like to quit his present office, to be made a collector of the customs at Newcastle or Hull? The change hinted at would be as sad a reverse to the navy surgeon. Gentlemen who have expended a small patrimony on the study of their profession, without half-pay must be left destitute. I speak from experience at the end of the former war. The feasibility which accompanies the professional character, must be deeply wounded by this neglect. In the duties of our station we become inmates with our officers; we mix in their friendships, and share in their confidence. We attend them in the hour of bodily affliction, when their inmost secrets, their dearest concerns are intrusted to us; and they often expire in our arms. This frequent communication learns us to partake

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of their heroism, and we grow jealous of every thing that detracts from the naval reputation of the country.”

“The neglected state of the naval hospitals arose partly from the small stipend of the medical officers; but this could not justify some occurrences that I must relate, and which I leave as a warning to others. To some these examples may appear disgusting; so they are to my eye. When I hear of the medical attendant of a public institution having accumulated thirty or forty thousand pounds by the private exercise of his profession; by an irresistible impulse of imagination the ghosts of so many thousands of brave men rise to my view, who have fallen into premature deaths by unprincipled neglect.

“At the beginning of this war a seaman fell from the top of a ship fitting at Plymouth, and was wounded dreadfully. He was immediately conveyed on shore, but nobody could be found to open the gate of the hospital. At last access was obtained; but not a surgeon could be found; he was attending a gentleman of great fortune in Cornwall. It is to be added, the man died of the hæmorrhage from his wound.

“A post-captain, so ill as to be carried on shore in his bed, came to sick-quarters, and, for the convenience of such attention as he required, to the house of a friend. The first visitor was a clerk, who demanded that he should come to the hospital and answer muster, or be *run* on the books. On the third day a private physician called upon him, saying that he came at the desire of the surgeon of the Royal Hospital, who was attending the *accouchement* of Lady M.—at sixty miles distance !”

Trotter was a fighter. As fleet physician he claimed the prerogative of a professional interest in everything that touched the welfare of the seamen, sick or well. “A very interesting circumstance took place on the 20th of May, 1800, at a general survey at the Royal Hospital, Plymouth, where I judged it proper to attend, on account of a large number of the Edgar and Pompee’s people being on the list for invaliding. These men had been sent on shore for fever; were now recovered, or convalescent; and brought forward for other complaints, or old hurts that never had been known to the surgeons of the respective ships.

“On entering the public room, I was accosted by Captain Creyke the governor, with his usual acuteness, and was asked by what authority I appeared there. To this I replied, the station I had the honour to hold. This was not deemed sufficient; he said he could only admit me by an Admiralty order. I then remarked, that the order for survey from the Port Admiral was addressed to Captains Stirling, Sawyer, and Pater, who were my officers, and to their opinions I would only submit. The captains very handsomely accepted of my attendance, as they knew I only came there with a view of

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benefit to service; and as they considered it their duty to obtain every evidence that could save a single man from being invalidated on false pretences. (Some time before this rencounter with the governor, in visiting some of the wards, I had dropped some angry expressions about bitters being put into the wine; which were artfully construed into interference with the medical practice. Remonstrances were immediately made to the Admiralty, seconded by the Board of Sick and Hurt; and their Lordships thought proper to restrict my visits. To this I made no reply, as I expected no support from Lord Bridport. Trusting to this order of the Admiralty, the governor thought he was empowered to exclude me from the hospital altogether. The captains present asserted their own authority, and the service triumphed. This business diffused general satisfaction throughout the fleet. This volume contains facts sufficient to justify a watchful eye over hospital establishments. The future surveys are reported to have been rather meliorated from my attendance. But on this occasion, had my opinion been taken, the whole of the Edgar's and Pompee's people should have been remanded to their ships without a single question being asked.) A general survey at an hospital has always been considered as a public day; and even on this occasion every surgeon of the fleet was present. An admiralty order directed my future attendance at all surveys afterwards."

It is proper in this connection to recall an earlier incident, showing that though Trotter stood for his rights he had worthy ideas of duty. "The salad, which I had represented in my letter to the Admiralty, as the best vegetables for our relief, was supplied in too small quantity to eradicate the disease. I wanted it to be given in large allowance to the different messes of the seamen; and that the fresh beef broth should be full of greens, or other pot-herbs. The lemons we could only consider for the cure. I demanded, therefore, five thousand pounds for daily consumption; and walked over the markets and gardens, to inform myself if this could be obtained. Our supply, hitherto, had seldom exceed *one hundred pounds* of lettuce, young onions, and mustard."

"The reader may smile at the idea of a Physician to a Fleet, attending the stalls at a vegetable market, or preambulating the country, to calculate the produce: but it never appeared to me below the dignity of the profession; nor did I consider it a mean task to serve the sallad with my own hands, from the Charon's quarterdeck."

"My station on board the Atlas not affording me opportunities to visit the sick as heretofore, or to communicate with the surgeons, I considered myself now rather as the register of their afflictions, than as the physician who ought to relieve them. This thought was

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transmitted where it was sure of being candidly treated; but my retirement was not deemed expedient.

“At this season I suggested that I could be much more usefully employed at the port of Plymouth, to inspect the health of the ships as they now refitted there. This was approved of; for, I believe, some persons were glad to get quit of me on any terms.”

“The people of the Saturn not being remarkable for cleanliness, suggested to me the necessity of having their bedding scoured at the hospital, as well as their cloathing. I therefore desired the Captain to insist upon it being done before his men returned on board. This was complied with; and for the *first time*, were infected blankets of seamen submitted to the purification of soap and water at a naval hospital. Who would suspect, that habits so unfavourable to health should exist in an hospital establishment; and at a time when most of our ships hold up such examples of cleanliness !—yet the expence of scouring a blanket only was three-pence.”

“On visiting the Captain’s people the third day after they were landed, in one of the wards of the south-east-wing, I found eleven patients without sheets to their beds; and on enquiring the cause at the nurse, I was informed that the matron was getting them ready as *fast as possible*. At this time the hospital was rather more than one third full !”

“The following order was issued from the Ville de Paris at sea:—
MAY 4th, 1800.

Memo.

It is my directions, that there are no sick in future to be sent to the hospital at Plymouth, from his Majesty’s ships and vessels under my command, without the authority of Dr. Trotter, physician to the fleet, who will visit the ships whenever a boat shall be sent to him for that purpose.

The respective Captains are to report to me, if, at any time, clothes or necessaries shall be sent from the hospital, with recovered men, uncleaned.

The Surgeons of the squadron are to send to Dr. Trotter a monthly state of the sick, from the 22d of April, 1800.

(Signed) ST. VINCENT.

“This order was the revival of medical discipline in the fleet; and restored my duties to the sick. But I received no intimation that an hospital ship should be fitted, which had before bestowed such unspeakable comforts to the Sick Berth.

“The order for the surgeons to furnish regular reports, puts it in my power to call upon them whenever a desire might be discovered for with-holding them, which was not frequently the case.

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“On consideration of the active duty of the ships that had cruized under Sir A. Gardner, all the winter, I represented to Earl St. Vincent the probable appearance of a prevailing scurvy; and my ideas on the prevention, from my experience and observations on the seasons and weather of the Channel. My opinion seemed to be treated with respect; and the fleet was informed, by his Lordship’s order, concerning the supply of vegetables, when arriving in port, as correctors of scurvy.

“Arrived the Temeraire, over-run with scurvy. R. A. Whitshed desired me to report to him, in writing, the condition of his people; I therefore recommended a fortnight’s allowance of fresh beef and vegetables, agreeable to the general practice in the fleet, to eradicate the disease.

“It appears that orders had been given, that no ship going to port, should be detained longer than six days. Unknown to me, a large supply of lemon juice was issued to every ship, as a preventive of scurvy, and ordered to be mixed with sugar and water, as lemonade. Before I was informed of this circumstance, I had recommended a sufficiency of fresh beef and vegetables to the Superb, which arrived a few days after. The Rear Admiral, who beheld this disease so general with great concern, I suppose, inclosed my Report to the Commander in Chief.”

“July.—Sometime in this month, I was honoured with the following laconic, epistle.

Ville De Paris, off Ushant,
July 15th.

Sir,

I very much disapprove your officious interference, to prevent His Majesty’s ships under my command from putting to sea, the moment their beer, water, and provisions are completed, which is ordered to be done with the utmost possible dispatch; and I desire you will discontinue this practice.

(Signed) ST. VINCENT.

To Dr. Trotter.

“On first perusing this letter I was rather at a loss to conjecture what it alluded to; but suspected that it must relate to reports given by order of R. A. Whitshed, on the prevailing scurvy in the Temeraire and Superb, mentioned above.

“On showing it to some of my friends in the fleet, they advised me to reply. To this I answered No: the temper that could dictate such a letter to a physician in the exercise of the best affections of the human heart, could not be satisfied with explanation. On such an occasion, if the medical character possesses any virtue within itself, to that he must fly for sanctuary; and let the storm rage that he cannot appease.

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“It needs scarcely to be mentioned, that this letter is incorrect in point of service, for a medical officer has no power to detain a ship. I acted in compliance with the order of the senior officer on the spot. But although my report prescribed a fortnight’s allowance of fresh meat and vegetables to these scorbutic crews, it did not imply that they should be detained a single hour in port; on the contrary, a month’s vegetables, in similar conditions of scurvy, have often been carried to sea.

“The harsh terms of this letter, I must confess wounded me grievously. I became tired of a station that exposed me to unmerited suffering. I had lately displeased one Commander in Chief by claiming protection from insult; and a second was now reproaching me while fulfilling the duties of my office.”

“It will not be wondered at, if after this transaction I resolved to trouble his Lordship no further with my correspondence; in this I was the more sorry, as I had cherished the hope, from his known discernment, to have pursued those plans of improvement in the medical department, which was left unfinished through the indisposition and retirement of Admiral Earl Howe.”

“Lord St. Vincent has directed the Sick Berths to be enlarged, and more commodiously fitted for the sick. What a pity he did not point out the Berth of the Centaur for a model.

“August. Fresh *vegetables* are now sent to sea with every ship for the use of the fleet; but it does not appear that any *live stock* have yet been ordered.

“All the ships which have lately arrived have much scurvy. In those cases where it has appeared the ounce of lemon juice, and the ounce of sugar mixed with water, which is Lord St. Vincent’s *formula*, do not seem to have checked its progress. A multitude of cases still occur, in which the surgeons are under the necessity of giving from six to eight ounces daily, in the usual manner, to effect a cure. The people in the Windsor Castle are evidently much emaciated by its use.

“Mr. Burd of the Temeraire, in his last report from sea remarks: ‘In consequence of the recruit which the ship’s company had in harbour, the general tendency to scurvy has disappeared. But it is still very marked, in many of those who were worst previous to our going into port; though even with them since coming to sea, by the use of lemon juice we gain ground. And I beg to remark, that their strength somewhat fails under its use; and emaciation of body is perceptible to the most inattentive observer.’

“Since the large allowance of sallad was served, the scurvy has continued to decline. The sudden change is wonderful. The squadron being now ordered to sea, the health of the men was considered equal to the expected cruise; but it could not be supposed

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secure against the effects of a sea diet, where vegetables and fresh beef had no share. The Surgeons were served from the Charon with boxes of lemons, in proportion to the progress of scurvy lately marked among the people, and thirty gallons of lemon-juice, to be used when the fruit was expended. I reserved two hundred and fifty gallons in the hospital ship, lest any unforeseen length of time, or exigencies of service, might keep the fleet at sea beyond what we foresaw.”

While attributing the highest honor to Lind, as the British champion of lemons in the treatment of scurvy, fully subscribing to their value, constantly agitating not only for their employment but for systematic and regular provision for a routine issue, Trotter considered it essential to make the general dietary adequate; that wine, fruit, green vegetables of all kinds, fresh bread, fresh meat, and general conditions favorable to health (ventilation, warm clothing, exercise) were even more important as preventive measures against scurvy than reliance on lemon juice alone.

“Whatever, therefore, may be the theory of sea-scurvy, we contend, that recent vegetable matter, imparts a *something* to the body, which fortifies it against the disease; and that in proportion to the quantity of this *something* imparted, making allowance, at the same time, for external causes, which counteract its effects on the constitution, the symptoms will sooner or later disappear. The preservative means ought, therefore, to be attended to, and we ought to trust only to the vegetable acid, when we can do no better. (It is the custom of service, for the purser to order his steward to buy vegetables, greens, or cabbages, for the fresh beef broth out of his necessary money; but there is no fixed quantity. There is a necessity for fixing the proportion, cost what it may. Why is an article of diet, that is the best security against a fatal disease, left to such uncertainty, or liable to be withheld by any individual, when its price becomes a little higher than common?).

“We have also found, that the preserved juice is very inferior to the fruit, in its entire and recent state; although, I believe, that great attention was paid to its preservation, and when there could be no suspicion of vinegar, or other acids, fraudulently added.”

He preferred the concentrated crystals to the juice, and was not in favor of general unrestricted use of lemon juice for everything. In time; the British service came to be supplied with what was supposed to be as good or better—the juice of West Indian limes instead of lemons—and the results were bad. It is scarcely necessary to remind the reader that we have here the original of our men’s popular designation for a vessel sailing under the British flag.

On one occasion Trotter recommended that, as large supplies of oranges and lemons were hard to come by, advantage be taken of the

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extreme cheapness of apples, selling in Devonshire at 1 shilling and 6 pence per hundred, to vary the antiscorbutic ration by this desirable and useful preventive. The admiralty was willing provided the board of sick and wounded judged it necessary. "These gentlemen, however, thought otherwise, by telling their lordships that they had provided a great quantity of fine onions at a small price, which, with lemon juice and vegetables, they esteemed equal to the correction of scurvy.

"Such was the opinion of two physicians sitting in a snug corner of Somerset-house, who neither heard the wind blow, or the tempest rage. The fleet off Ushant, it is true, had large supplies for preventing scurvy; but if a saving of public money could be made, by supplying articles of equal efficacy, and more desirable under the circumstances of service, I have no hesitation in saying, it ought to have been done. On inquiry at the agent of the Royal Hospital, I learned that no change had been made in the purchase of onions for the fleet.

"Query. How long would these Commissioners of Sick and Hurt like to live on onions and lemon-juice, as preventives of scurvy, in a dreary winter cruise of twenty weeks, off the black rocks at the entrance of Brest harbour?

"While it is my duty to prescribe rules of health to a fleet of brave men, secluded from the comforts of the land, God ! of Mercy ! remind me of the Christian precept, *to do as I would be done unto!*"

"Admiral Lord Bridport came to Portsmouth about this time, to take the command of fourteen sail of the line. He had heard of the general scurvy, but supposed, from the orders given some time ago, by the Admiralty, that it was effectually overcome. His Lordship received my opinion on the subject with much attention, and entered earnestly into my manner of curing it. He desired the resident Commissioner of Sick and Wounded to order the quantity which I deemed necessary, whether it could be procured at Portsmouth, Gosport, or elsewhere. It was of little moment whether the sallad ought to be considered as a part of victualling, or medicine; the public service demanded instant relief. Had it been in my power to command it, it should have been brought from the Land's-end, in Cornwall, before the fleet had so long groaned under the affliction. We have heard of a Minister ordering a train of ordnance across the country, from Woolwich to Portsmouth, to save time; in this manner would I have wheeled the product of every distant garden to Portsmouth, lest the tooth of a sailor should drop from his gums, by a tardy conveyance of his deliverer.

'Deliberat Roma, perit Saguntum.' "

Trotter was always harping on ventilation. "No department of service is more frequently the subject of conversation among officers and surgeons than the ventilation of ships. But although all are agreed, that a pure atmosphere is the object to be obtained, the ways

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and means of effecting it are very different in different ships, so that as much quackery is displayed in this, as in any process of duty that we are acquainted with. One Captain is jealous of seeing the least moisture on his decks, while another orders them to be drenched with salt water every morning. Some contend for the purity of a hold, that is corrected by frequent, or constant fires, while others trust to the daily admission of clear water, for the perfect salubrity of the well, etc.

“The method of extracting foul airs from the lowest apartments of ships, has employed mechanical philosophy for a length of time, to invent and adapt an apparatus and instrument for that purpose. Afore attention has therefore been directed to the construction of pumps for dislodging a vitiated portion, than has been bestowed on a machine that should fill up the vacuum by a purer column. For when a quantity of foul air is extracted by the pump from the hold, the portion that rushes in is not a part of the pure external atmosphere, but what comes from the decks, already much exhausted of its salubrious quality.

“The history of Mr. Sutton’s invention of airpipes for ventilating ships, to be found in Dr. Meade’s works, affords many striking instances of those rebuffs, which ingenious men too frequently experience from public boards, public offices, etc.”

“We need scarcely hint that the best substitute for washing decks is *dry rubbing with sand*. This practice fortunately gains ground; it affords a wholesome exercise for the people; and it has been well exemplified in the best regulated ships, that their decks look better than those drenched so frequently with salt water. This salutary reformation has probably saved more lives than any other alteration whatever. *Whitewashing*, at all time so delicate and cleanly, makes a part of this plan, and excites ideas of personal cleanliness among the people.”

“The scuttles, and sometimes a few ports, are opened for ventilation. But these have their inconveniences. The man who lies nearest the scuttle finds the current disagreeable, and often shuts it. In harbours locked by high lands, it is a good plan to keep the ship's broad-side to the wind, by a spring on the cable. Much however might be done by having air-flews, so constructed as to communicate with the upper part of the ship, raised some feet above the gunwale, with scuttles fitted to open, as the wind may be on the beam, or otherwise. The lower end of these ought to come within two feet of the lower-deck; by which means the current of air would be diffused aboard, without blowing partially on any particular sleeping place. A very equal circulation would in this manner be maintained, when there was a necessity of laying tarpaulins over the hatches to keep out rain, or when wind-sails could not be put down to advantage in

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bad weather. The Medusa, hospital ship, was fitted at Plymouth with air-shafts of this description, and, when duly attended, kept the hospital sufficiently ventilated. We can find no objection, as far as we have conversed with officers, to their general introduction throughout the navy: they can be so constructed as to be clear of the guns and ropes; and when we consider the great advantages of pure air to life and health, we ardently wish to see the trial.

“A ventilator constructed nearly on these principles may be seen on board the Barfleur, the contrivance of Rear Admiral Collingwood; and the Admiral, with great justice, attributes a large share of the improved health of his ship’s company, to this flow for conducting from the lower parts of the deck, the air vitiated by respiration.”

“In the well-regulated ship, where one of the main-top-mast stunsails, from its commodious size, is usually converted into a wind-sail, the lower end is generally put so low as the hatch of the main hold: and when the fore-hatch is kept open, that part of the hold is of course well refreshed. But the whole bottom of the ship cannot be purified in this manner, the spirit-room being surrounded by bulkheads that are water-tight, for the security against fire. The bread-room ought to have a wind-sail to itself; and the forepart, which is commonly a close bulk-head, ought either to be grated, or constructed with folding-doors, to be laid open as often as may be found necessary. I consider the bread-room of a ship, from its present pent-up condition, the number of lights so frequently burning in it, and the noxious effluvia issuing from cheese, etc. as a species of volcano that is constantly throwing out pestiferous fumes to shorten and weaken life.”

“We think a very commodious apparatus for ventilation might be constructed on the principle of the common bellows. This machine ought to be placed on the quarter-deck, or booms, over the waist, that no air might be thrown down but what is perfectly pure. Long leathern tubes being fitted to the nasal of the bellows, would by this contrivance convey a current of wind into every corner below, as you choosed to direct the mouth of the tube.

“The instruments now in use for extracting foul airs, are as much adapted to the purpose as the intention required; but the air which rushes in, to restore the place of that just extracted, gives no additional purity, unless a fresh column is flowing in from the upper parts of the ship. This shows the great necessity of flews and wind-sails, that no portion may be ever permitted to stagnate below, but a constant circulation throughout the whole preserved.”

“In such situations of naval service, the able officer of a ship will be distinguished from the man of inferior abilities; and as far as it is possible, in the execution of duty, he will endeavour to give his

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people no unnecessary toil. The rule for that must always be, that the refreshment from sleep at night should be equal to the fatigues of the day. The strength of a ship's company will thereby be reserved improper occasions, for the hour of battle, or severe gales of wind...

"The nice criterion of discipline is to give seamen full employment without making duty a toil, and in all situations to remember they are men !"

"The best cures which I have witnessed during this prevailing malady, appeared to have been more owing to regimen than medicine. These happened in ships that had greater advantages of diet than others; and where the patient had not been weakened in the early stage of bleeding, under the idea of relieving stricture of the breast, as a supposed attendant of pneumonia.

"A multitude of cases have however been presented to me at different times, under the appellation of phthisis, that I believe had no disposition towards it. Uncommon recoveries have therefore been said to take place, as the effects of particular articles of medicine and superior treatment. All accounts of this kind are to be trusted with some qualification. Miraculous cures, even in the stage of purulency, have been talked of; but at the same time so vaguely detailed, and with such total neglect of the operation of other powers on the body, that little credit is to be given to their histories."

In discussing the prevalence and increase of nervous diseases due to the restlessness and excessive activity of modern life he reverts again to the impressment of sailors: "It is the fate of war that numbers of seamen are brought into the naval service against their inclinations; many of those under circumstances singularly severe; as happen to men that are impressed immediately on coming from foreign voyages, without even hearing of their relations, far less having a sight of their families. Nostalgia, which I take to be only a variety of hypochondriasis, is sometimes strongly marked in these cases, and emphatically speaks the language of human nature. How disgraceful is this practice to a nation that calls itself the most free on the face of the earth, that deprives of the privilege of citizenship those men to whom it owes its security, and to whose valour the sound of applause has been constantly heard! But it seems that only empty praises are returned for the first of all sacrifices, a surrender of their liberty. The present war has given birth to much warmth in the discussion of political subjects. But what authority can justify the involuntary service of any particular class of men? African slavery has been discussed among us; but, though Christianity is the national religion, there seems so little of the spirit of it in the country, that the slave-trade still continues, and ought to continue, if there is no remedy against impressing seamen."

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“We also, on many occasions, meet with young officers, as well as old ones, of all descriptions, whose sensibility has long smarted under unmerited disappointment of honours in the line of their profession. Can any misfortune in life be more galling to a brave man, conscious of his right to promotion, than to see another preferred before him, without even a single pretension? Disappointments of this nature have brought many worthy officers to an early grave, and induced afflictions of body and mind that nothing beside could have produced. Ye rulers of the earth ! Ye dispensers of honours I whom high heaven had deputed to do justice here below, remember that there is another world, where all your favours will undergo a scrutiny, and be tried as in a balance !”

Trotter was a great believer in horseback riding: “This besides the exercise and motion which it affords, presents a variety of images to the mind, which cannot fail to introduce a new train of ideas, and thus re-act on the body, but particularly on the stomach and intestines. This seldom fails to do good; and, if the ship is allowed to remain a fortnight in port during clear weather, a cure is obtained without much medicine. Exercise on horseback, as being so opposite to any kind of muscular action or amusement that can be obtained on board, is, to the sea-officer, by far the most salutary.”

The dullness of life at a hospital and its depressing effects in certain nervous disorders are thus referred to:

“The naval hospitals are very little to be preferred to a ship in the treatment of this disease. They afford no amusement to seamen, and the great pleasure in coming on shore is to make the best use of their cunning to be put down on the list of invalids. [The author means persons to be invalided from the service.] All energy of mind is lost within these walls, and must be, till some means are devised by officers of address and intelligence to shake off that languor and indolence which we observe so general in the wards.”

Trotter was anxious for a board of health to be established which would have power to compel the adoption and employment of measures recognized as salutary, but neglected through the greed, parsimony, or indifference of commercial firms, government officials, etc.

Trotter was an earnest advocate of compulsory vaccination and a great admirer of Jenner, to whom he transmitted a gold medal for which he had been instrumental in raising subscriptions from some 80 medical officers of the navy. It was not until 1858 that this step was adopted; meanwhile the disease was rampant in certain communities and aboard the ships of the navy. Trotter repeatedly made representations on the subject to the admiralty but without success, but in 1800 an order was issued by the commissioners of sick and

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wounded to *permit* the surgeons to inoculate any of the seamen who were “desirous of it.”

“Thus, these physicians have at last condescended to give an opinion on this popular practice: excellent humanists ! There is scarcely a village in Great Britain that has not long shared of its blessings; and six months ago the Government of France borrowed a British physician. Dr. Woodville of the Small-Pox Hospital, to introduce it into Paris !

“At this time the Board of Sick and Wounded sent to the Royal Hospital at Plymouth a few lancets armed with vaccine matter, with directions, that if these should fail in communicating the disease, the medical staff of the hospital should send by the coach to London *two children* to bring down the infection of the fleet. Would it not have been preferable to send a Gloucestershire cow, as proposed in my second Volume? Before this time one thousand children had been inoculated in the vicinity of Plymouth for the vaccine disease, at which port our ships refitted.”

From the hospital ship *Medusa* in 1797 Trotter had urged on the admiralty the importance of separate wards or buildings for small-pox at Haslar and other hospitals. “For these reasons and for many others, too minute to be detailed here. I beg leave to suggest to their Lordships some building, to be constructed at a sufficient distance from the hospitals, solely for the reception of Small-Pox, with kitchen, *washhouse*, etc. entirely confined to this institution.”

“My proposal received due attention from their Lordships, and was submitted to the consideration of the Commissioners of Sick and Wounded; and their report was transmitted to me, which was briefly, that they did not see any necessity for a small-pox ward at a distance from the other hospitals. A subject of such moment had a claim to all the attention that could be given it; and the evidence which we have produced appears to us convincing. We think that a small building in the most retired part of the hospital-ground at Haslar and Plymouth, a small area round it for the benefit of convalescents, with a kitchen and washhouse, to cut off all communication with other patients, might be erected for a trilling sum.

“Some improvement, however, took place in consequence of this representation. A door communicating with the common staircase of other wards was built up; but let any person consider the facility with which this disease is imported, and let him examine the situation of small-pox wards at these hospitals, and he will not fail to think as we do... When we, in the fleet, have so often followed up its source to the hospitals; is it not likely that it also is carried from them to the neighbouring towns, and kept constantly alive. We moreover contend that it is inconsistent with the spirit of medical jurisprudence to admit the small-pox infection within an

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hospital with other diseases, to whom it is liable to be conveyed; we therefore choose to *record* the fact, that it may benefit posterity. 'If Rome must fall, we are innocent.'

"We shall hope to see some of the Gloucestershire cows transferred to the navy farm, that surrounds the walls of Haslar Hospital, for the purpose of inoculating the whole seamen at Spithead, and thus prevent any return of that infection into our ships of war, that we are now employed to defeat."

"Within the last three years of the war, and particularly in 1800, the instances of variolous infection being brought on board of the ships of the fleet were more numerous than on any former occasion. The disease at that time, in the natural way, was very general in the populous towns of Plymouth, Plymouth-Dock, and Stonehouse. The seamen, while on shore at liberty, were more than usually exposed, from the number of public houses that had lately been opened in the vicinity, and multiplied the sources of this as well as all other kinds of infection. I have only marked a few of those instances, as they appeared in the general history of health, where something particular had happened. In a multitude of them the infection had been carried on board by children in their mother's arms. Surely it ought to be strongly enforced in our code of naval discipline to prevent the introduction of small-pox. The Master at Arms usually attends at the gang-way to search the women for spirituous liquors; and at the same time he might with equal ease inspect the children, and where any suspicious eruptions, such as the small-pox, measles, or itch, appear, the surgeon of the ship ought to be called to decide on the propriety of admitting the woman or child. Where the disease is in danger of extending, inoculation cannot be too early practiced."

"Our experience continues to confirm the opinion formerly given, that small-pox cannot give out infection till *the third day*. This fact is of much importance in easing the minds of those who are in danger; and affords some certainty to means of prevention and early separation."

"While the vaccine inoculation was thus beginning, and meeting very general support, the medical officers of the British navy were not inattentive to the subject; and very early attempts were made to introduce it among the seamen. But all these have been only partially followed up; and at the time I am writing it seems entirely given over. In the summer of 1800 I requested permission of the Admiralty to introduce it into the ships of the fleet, with a view of procuring full authority, that all prejudices might be obviated which could rise against it. This was however not thought to be the proper channel for such an undertaking; it fell into other hands, and, as was foreseen, soon became neglected. It would have been an easy matter for me to have directed the practice in every ship as she arrived from

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sea. In those instances where the variolous infection had been carried on board, and where I *personally* addressed the seamen on the safety of the vaccine inoculation, the measure was easily accomplished. Much good might therefore have been done with very little trouble: of two thousand men and upwards in the fleet who never had the small-pox, scarcely two hundred were inoculated with the cow-pox; and the remainder are left still exposed to a dangerous disease, whenever it may come in their way.”

“The surgeon found thirty men who were unconscious of having had small-pox; this infection was brought on board by a woman of the town, who had buried her child the day before, and died of that disease; so that it had been carried in her wearing apparel. The men first taken ill messed with this woman, and sickened about the seventh day.”

Fever of a malignant type and smallpox broke out on the *Orion*, Sir. J. Sumarez, commanding: “Some of these patients had symptoms of considerable malignity; and three of the number died on the fifth day from being seized. No nurse or attendant in our hospital was infected: I attributed this solely to the extreme exact attention to cleanliness, both in the persons of the sick, their body, linen, and bedding; a boiler with water was kept in constant readiness to wash every article of clothing as soon as it came from the beds of the sick, and a tub stood by for this purpose. Not even a handkerchief or night-cap was laid away till washed and aired. Only one patient died in the small-pox; which were of a milder kind than usually met with in adult subjects. As it was likely that the disease must now extend itself to every one on board the *Orion*, who had never been infected, people of this description, to the number of fifteen, were called to the quarter deck, and admonished by the captain and myself, to submit to inoculation, as an easy and safe mode of getting over the disease. Some of their prejudices, however, were not easily overcome; they were of the religious kind, and they did not consider it right to bring a disorder upon themselves. We combated this objection with the usual arguments, that Providence had put into our power the means of escaping a dreadful distemper by a trifling operation, and that it was impious in human beings to neglect it. They felt our advice more sensibly when they were told, that we considered it our duty to instruct them for their welfare, and that our only motive was their safety, for they were not to be compelled to undergo inoculation; but act as they pleased. I added, that two or three general inoculations of seamen had taken place on board the *Charon*, not one of whom had ever been confined an hour to bed. Ten of the fifteen consented to be inoculated, and had the disease in its mildest degree; the other five were doubtful of having had it in their infancy, and were not infected.”

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“In the small-pox, the disease seems incapable of infecting another person, before the second or third day of the eruption. This has enabled us to remove patients into the hospital and hospital-ship, after the disease was ascertained, so as to secure others from being affected. We have seen this in the Gibraltar, Valiant, Queen Charlotte, etc. In measles, however, this does not seem to hold good. The disease may be propagated at the most early stage of eruption; and if I was to be allowed a conjecture on the subject, I would say, that the contagion is the offspring of the catarrh which accompanies the measles.”

Trotter’s appointment as physician to His Majesty’s fleet, under command of Admiral Howe, was on April 3, 1794, and on April 9 he was ordered to the hospital ship *Charon*. By the 16th of the month he had visited all the ships (32 sail of the line, 8 frigates, a sloop, a fire ship, 1 cutter, and 2 luggers) and submitted a tabular statement regarding the health of the personnel.

“It deserves to be recorded to the immortal honour of the officers in this Fleet, that the stock of their messes, consisting of sheep and poultry, with all the delicacies which their tables afforded, was cheerfully resigned for the support and comfort of the wounded. But their goodness did not stop here; they learned that the diet of the hospital was deficient in some articles which a wounded sailor could wish for; and sums of money were sent to procure them. My heart warms with indescribable emotions, while I relate a fact that deserves to be recorded with the pen of an angel.” In June the fleet engaged the enemy and there were many wounded.

In July considerable sickness prevailed: “The infected ships, during the Month of July were employed in the means of stopping the contagion. Those officers who had confidence in fumigation, performed it every morning: the decks were kept clean, and the whole inside white-washed: constant attention was paid to the cleanliness of the people’s cloaths, and the bedding was spread abroad every day to air. The seamen were ordered to keep themselves clean in their persons, and to shift more frequently. Fires were kindled in pots in the hold, well, and bread-room; stoves in the orlop, cable-tiers, and fore and after cockpits. Care was taken that the circulation of air through the wings should not be interrupted; and, besides the common windsails, two stunsails were fitted for the fore and main hatchway, so that every corner below was pure and compleatly perflated by the air; some of these sails were kept trimmed during the night, so as to counteract the effects of the heat when the ports were down. A quantity of vinegar in an iron pot was frequently, in the course of the day, converted into vapor, by plunging a red hot loggerhead into it, or sprinkled over the decks. Such were the method which our officers persisted in; besides, the cables, sails, cordage, with all kinds of stores, were brought upon deck during

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the day, and the store-rooms, in the mean time, were ventilated and white-washed, so that not a particle of impure air could lodge any where. The immediate separation of the infected was, however, what I most depended upon; and not even the slightest cases were allowed to remain in the ship. The surgeons were directed to order their mates to walk frequently round the deck; and to watch those men who, while sitting in their berths, appeared dejected or solitary. This was always my own practice in an infected ship because seamen will sometimes withhold their complaints for a day or two, under the idea that an incipient fever is only a common cold.”

“It having appeared to me, during the late operations of the fleet at sea, that the diet of the hospital ship was extremely deficient, in articles of comfort for the sick, which induced me to apply for some addition; the Lords of the Admiralty were pleased to comply with my application. We were now enabled to carry with us stock and vegetables, fruit, pickles, eggs, porter, etc. and to purchase milk, when in port.”

Very interesting, after our experiences of 1917-18, are the references to influenza epidemics in the British fleets in 1782 and 1795: “In the year 1782, a similar catarrh prevailed in the Channel Fleet, then in the North Sea, under the command of Earl Howe. It spread with inconceivable rapidity over the whole. The fleet was obliged to return to port, and it was some time before the disease disappeared: a considerable number of deaths was the consequence.” It prevailed to such a degree, in the spring of 1782, as to render the ships almost inactive. The disease was then general throughout Europe: it spread from the shores of the Baltic to Holland and the Low Countries, from thence to England.” ... “The signal was made to unmoor or get under weigh in the morning; but the officers could not get the men out of their hammocks. It was in vain that they used threats, the people declared that they were unable to move. The surgeon and mates were sent for, who soon pronounced, that they were labouring under a violent disease. This was communicated to the Admiral; who doubted the report, and sent three captains with their surgeons, to examine the state of the Fortitude’s ship’s company. The captain found it exactly as related; the ship was ordered to Plymouth, where numbers of her crew were landed at the hospital. The other ships had not been two days at sea, till their situation was as bad as that of the Fortitude; some of them could scarcely muster seamen to take in sail: the whole returned to port.

“In the mean time, the Fleet in the North Sea suffered from the Catarrh in an equal degree; and was obliged to return to port to recruit the people. Some deaths happened in consequence.

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“On the 17th of January 1795, the weather then very severe, and the thermometer at 17° of Fahrenheit, I was ordered to examine the state of the Cumberland, just arrived from the Nore, where she had been lately commissioned. I found one hundred and twenty men ill of Catarrh. The symptoms, however, were in general slight, with no oppression on the breast, and none were confined to bed: a few of the worst were sent to the hospital. As the acquisition of a 74 gun ship was of some importance at this time, the enemy’s fleet being at sea, I recommended what was deemed needful in such a condition, and reported the ship fit for sea. Captain Rowley was active and careful in making the sick comfortable. He procured the whole, additional warm cloathing, particularly flannel jackets, which were the more valuable, as a great part of the crew had lately returned from the East Indies in the Vengeance. Care was also taken not to expose them to unnecessary cold and wet weather. Directions were immediately given to abstain from washing, to substitute scraping and rubbing with dry sand, additional fires were lighted on the lower deck. The sick list decreased from this time, and the Cumberland did well.

“A few days after my visit to the Cumberland, I was ordered to report to the Admiral the state of the Colossus from the number of sick, upwards of seventy, being returned in the weekly account. This disease was a Catarrh; and some were sent on shore with symptoms of inflammation, considerably greater than any in the other ship. The Colossus appeared to me to have her sickness much aggravated by washing decks; although I found that Captain Jenkins, then her first lieutenant, had opposed the practice, and represented it as hurtful. It was afterwards laid aside. The Colossus did not suffer from any future increase of the sick list, during the cruize.

“The Fleet being obliged to put into Torbay, in the beginning of February, we there experienced some severe weather. The Catarrh was now general in every ship. Some bad cases appeared in the Brunswick, Canada, and Prince of Wales. In the latter ship it assumed very much the type of a pure Typhus, with weak frequent pulse, dejection of countenance, great muscular debility, and stupor.”

“When the catarrh was epidemic in 1782, I was surgeon of the Bustler sloop of war, at Plymouth: I was affected with the disease in a severe degree. In the present case I was also a sufferer, and had a relapse, from exposing myself too soon in the boat, to rain and cold weather, in Torbay.”

Trotter’s figures show that between January 18 and February 28 there were 5,300 cases in the fleet; that is, cases severe enough to be admitted to the sick list.

In July, 1796, Trotter addressed the Admiralty on the subject of contagion and disinfection, expressing emphatic disapproval of

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the nitrous acid method which had recently received its favorable action. He repeated his views on cleanliness, isolation, prompt removal of the sick as the harborers of the contagion, and urged the employment of air flues or pipes to facilitate the escape of the foul air from the decks where people sleep.

“If it is found necessary in medical practice, in order to make attendants careful in their duty to the sick, to keep up their confidence in the preservative means against infection; I see no necessity for having recourse to deception, or the pious fraud of a placebo. Let the nurses of hospitals who attend patients in infectious fevers, be impressed with the idea, that if they shift the sick man often, in bed-cloathes and body-linen; keep him clean in his person, by frequent ablution, and change the air of the ward very frequently; that it will not only recover the patient, but will infallibly prevent other persons from being infected. Truth that soon decides doubts, will quickly assure every nurse, that this is the only certain method of prevention; and it is the only guide that ought to regulate the conduct of a physician.”

He confesses to very little confidence in the power of drugs to cure typhus, suggests the need of studying a large number of cases comparatively, and of being slow to attribute unusual virtue to a remedy which appeared effective, since coincidentally with its use the severity of the epidemic might have been declining.

In treating malaria Trotter reports the best results from administering cinchona every half hour for four hours before the expected paroxysm, esteeming a given amount thus used three times as efficient as when given during the whole intermission.

In speaking of yellow fever Trotter praises Rush, of Philadelphia. He goes on to deplore the dissipated habits of some of the officers embarked for the West Indies and to advise a reduction of the meat ration on going to the Tropics. Where heavy work has to be done in the noon hours it is the part of wisdom to employ natives for it.

I would recommend a strict official return to be called, from every physician and surgeon now in the West Indies; and a detail of the method of treatment in the Fever, down to the minutest circumstance of medicine, diet, and regimen. This return would no doubt exhibit a gloomy catalogue of mortality; but it might go a great way to prevent a repetition of the scene. If accurate vouchers are required for every two-penny nail, or yard of cordage, how much more are they required for the safety and cure of a brave sailor or soldier?

“Might not some method for generating artificial cold, be of service in this fever? I should like to know the effects of wrapping the body, for a length of time, in wet linen, some how after the fashion of cooling wine by suspending it in canvass bags, frequently sprinkled with water; such a trial is perfectly consistent with the most approved

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opinions on the nature of the Yellow Fever; but it must be done during the inflammatory stage.”

Discussing the health of seamen and the health of the fleet Trotter utters much wisdom: “Upon the first outfit of a ship, the men received on board her, should be examined with the most scrupulous attention, that disordered and infectious, or foul ulcerous persons may not be admitted. Such of their cloaths as are foul, and of little worth, should be destroyed, and the residue washed and fumigated; and their persons should also be thoroughly cleansed, by causing them to be washed with soap and water from head to foot. Their hair, if neglected and filthy, should be cut short, and if necessary their heads should be shaved.”

“The nature of cleanliness too is often misunderstood; and I know of nothing of that kind which is so much mistaken, as the too frequent and indiscreet drenching the decks, and more especially those where the people sleep, with water, and particularly in cold latitudes during the winter. By this means I have known dreadful sickness *introduced*, and I have known it *removed* by a contrary practice. It would be deemed extravagant to advance an opinion, that the decks should never be washed; but I feel no reluctance in making a direct assertion, that it were far better that they should not be *washed at all*, than with that want of discretion and precaution, which so generally prevails.”

“Their hammocks should be kept clean; but whenever they are washed, they never should be permitted to sleep in them until they are perfectly dry; for they had better spread their bedding on the deck, than lie in a damp hammock.”

“Nothing is more commendable, or has a better effect on the people, than parade, order, and regularity in a ship of war; but these things should always be subservient to the health of the men. In line of battle ships, the ports being up and the guns run out, has a fine appearance; but, in this case, the health of the crew should be consulted; for in cold damp weather, and particularly when the ship is broadside to the wind, the exposing of the men to a current of air on such occasions, and when too they are in an inactive state, is extremely detrimental to their health, and brings on a train of dismal disorders. At these times the weather ports should be shut. A frame to fit every port, with double bunting stitched to it, is an excellent method to correct the evil consequences of too great a current of air passing through the ship at improper seasons. It prevents the ill effects of too much air, but admits enough for sufficient ventilation.”

“The boats crews of a ship are generally ragged as well as sickly. They too often sell their clothes to buy *liquor*, but too often also they

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part with them to buy food, on account of their being unnecessarily kept on shore, to the loss of their regular meals with the rest of the ship's company. It may with truth be said, that the inattention to the boat's crews of his Majesty's ships, is amongst the principal irregularities in the navy that require correction; for it destroys their health, and is a great cause of desertion.

"Amongst the various omissions which contribute to the injury of the health of the crews of his Majesty's ships, nothing seems more extraordinary than the general neglect there is of working the fixed ventilators. These should never stand still for a moment. A boy is capable of working them, and it may also be made a little extra duty for such as may be guilty of very slight offences."

"As soap has not yet been fully introduced to supply the people, the captains would do well to insert an article into their private orders, for the men to buy it at pay-day, and to be mustered with their cloathing at stated times."

"The Medusa, a 50-gun ship, having been fitted at Plymouth as an hospital ship to attend the fleet, I have been directed by the Lords Commissioners of Admiralty to take up my residence on board as soon as she arrives at Spithead.

"In the mean time, at my request, their Lordships have been pleased to order the same *improved diet* to be supplied as was customary in the Charon, with the addition of a milch cow, which may be considered the last article of comfort that we can suggest as practicable to be carried to sea: this gave all we could wish, without any unnecessary refinement."

"February 3d. The squadron returned to Spithead, in good health, without meeting the French fleet.

"The surgeons of the fleet at this time were served with a new code of instructions from the Board of Sick and Wounded, which now had the appointment of surgeons and mates throughout the navy. We observe, among some alterations, a very complicated form of journal: and what is rather singular, a weekly account is required to be sent every opportunity to the Board: the use of nitrous gas is also directed to be used to destroy contagion when it appears in his Majesty's ships."

"May 1st. The Medusa hospital ship joined the fleet at St. Helens, now complete in every thing that I could devise, for the comfort of the sick.

"14th. The hospital ship left the fleet off Plymouth.

"15th. Arrived at Spithead, and landed the sick; the weather fine.

"July 8th. Having completed our stores and necessaries, sailed from St. Helen's to join the fleet.

"12th. Joined the fleet in Torbay.

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“The scurvy had appeared in most of the ships during the cruize, but cured with ease on board.

“16th. Received the sick of the fleet, to the number of fifty-four, chiefly ulcers and pulmonic complaints.

“17th. The fleet sailed, and also the Medusa with the above-mentioned sick on board.

“August 5th. Received the hospital stores, and sixty sheep to be distributed.

“6th. Joined the fleet, and distributed the necessaries, vegetables, stock, etc.

“20th. This day a seaman’s wife was brought from La Pique, in the eighth month of pregnancy, subject to constant hysterics, and incessant reachings and vomiting. She was allowed one of the nurse’s cabins, with suitable attendants. These complaints had been of some weeks standing, but seemed to increase as the uterus extended; and she was now extremely miserable. The usual routine of medicines, opium, castor, asafoetida, camphor, aether, etc., were tried in vain: lying on her back with the pelvis somewhat elevated, was the only posture that gave any relief. Every thing in the way of diet was quickly thrown from her stomach, and she seldom slept. In this state she continued till the ship came to Torbay, where she had relations, and was delivered of a healthy child the morning after she landed: from this time all her complaints ceased.”

Incredible as it may seem, in view of our standards to-day, it is a well-authenticated fact that in the eighteenth century when a ship reached a home port it was immediately invaded by women, who took up their residence on board by the hundreds and remained until her departure. They usually attempted, in spite of the routine search at the gangway, to bring liquor aboard so as to increase their welcome, though this was unnecessary, as the tars were eager for their presence and hung over the side to pick out the prettiest as the watermen rowed them alongside. If a girl was not chosen she had to go ashore and the boatman got no fee for his trouble. Dancing, amorous dalliance, intoxication, now succeeded the slavery of sea life. When the time came to get up anchor the marines would clear the ship of the fair guests amid tears, outcries, lamentations, and piteous appeals to be allowed to remain aboard for the voyage. Occasionally a few enlisted men of unusual merit and standing were allowed to take their wives along.

“Some of our correspondents still regret that soap has never yet been issued by authority, through the pursers. We think it would be a great piece of economy to supply seamen with that kind of soap for washing that *lathers* with salt water. The Portuguese make a soap of this kind on the coast of Africa; but it might be done in England:

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it depends on a larger portion of alkali, which adds a little to the price. This practice would save fresh water; and it must always be deemed a severe restriction when the people are not allowed water for washing: on many occasions it would be preferable to deny them drink rather than prevent regular cleanliness.”

Trotter was always distressed and shocked, both as a physician and as a man, by excess in drink and preached the evil consequences of intemperance on every suitable occasion. He was a firm believer in the medicinal value of alcohol and not opposed to the issue, in moderation, of rations of good beer, etc. In August, 1800, he addressed the admiralty on the subject of better policing of the city of Plymouth and of reducing the number of gin mills there operating disastrously to the health and morals of the sailors.

“Although the subject of this letter may in some respects be deemed foreign to the department of medicine; yet, as connected with it in others in the general plan of preserving health in the fleet; I shall hope to be forgiven as an executive medical officer in requesting the attention of their Lordships to what may be conceived of more importance to naval service, than any thing which I have had the honour, for a length of time, to submit to their deliberation. Since the ships of the fleet have chiefly refitted at the Western ports: and the pay as well as prize-money of the whole have been paid at Plymouth, an unusual influx of money has of course taken place in these towns; but especially at Plymouth Dock. Where so large a number of seamen, from the increased number of ships in the fleet, have occasion to spend their wages, those tumults and excesses, the common offspring of their irregularities, when unrestrained by discipline, have multiplied in proportion... The inhabitants of this place, in order to avail themselves fully of the rich harvest which the profusion of the seamen is daily boding forth, have, by interest and address, with the neighbouring magistrates, opened, within these eight months, not less than one hundred and forty *additional* public houses in the town of Dock only... A certain number of houses have, by the strong grasp of avarice, been pitched upon for the purpose of gin-shops; and if the present inhabitant did not chuse to take out the licence for vending liquors, he was turned out of doors, and his house made over to somebody else. If such is the prevailing practice, their Lordships must be aware into what dangerous society the heedless and improvident seamen may be decoyed. In resorts of this description the general mutiny of 1797 was first planned; there the Irish catholic priests took up their abode, when they swore in the United Irishmen of the fleet to extirpate every protestant in our ships; and there also the crimps are concealed, that delude and persuade our seamen to desertion. Such is the degraded state of police of this town containing upwards of 25,000 inhabitants I

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“It is by no means my intention, in this letter, to abridge the pleasures of the seamen; but I am humbly of opinion that much might be done to restrain their excesses, to meliorate their moral character, and to guard them against imposition; which would redound to the public benefit... There is scarcely a day that I walk from my lodgings to the boat, but some of the horrors that I am now reprobating fall under my view. In those conflicts, which during a state of ebriety the seamen have among themselves so frequently in the streets, nothing can exceed the savage apathy with which they are beheld by the inhabitants, who value them only as the dupes of extortion; and look on, while they half-murder one another, with ferocious pleasure.

“What I would venture to recommend on this subject, is a total change in the administration of the police, and to be conducted after the model of Westminster. No person would then be permitted to open a public house but people of unexceptionable character; and constables or other officers might be so arranged to patrol the streets, as to prevent riot and disorder. The seaman would thus learn to spend his wages with decency, and return in due time to his ship, without endangering his health or his life, by continued intoxication. A police of this description, under respectable magistrates, would introduce a new æra into naval service; would be a most effectual check, and tend to extinguish that licentious spirit that has gone abroad among our seamen; and which runs much hazard of being renewed with fresh horrors in the event of paying off the ships at a general peace.—I have the honour to be, etc.”

The admiralty promptly referred the letter to the Duke of Portland, one of the secretaries of state, asking that steps be taken to correct the evils reported.

“I have observed for some time past, that the ships coming into Hamoaze to refit, soon suffer from the excess of the people on shore. A week has sometimes done more harm than a cruise of five months; and not to be wondered at, since two hundred public houses have been opened in Dock, and its neighbourhood in addition to what were licensed before, within the last twelve months ! Every walk or lane which the sailor is used to frequent, is now crowded with gin-shops.—I addressed another letter to the Admiralty on this subject.”

“January 10th. The Glory, now refitting in Hamoaze, has, since the end of November, sent upwards of fifty men to the hospital, some in typhus, caught in the filthy stews of Dock, or produced by the poisonous spirits sold there. These cases exhibit in afflicting but real characters the account of which I some time ago sent to the Admiralty, of the increased numbers of public houses opened in Plymouth Dock, perhaps at this moment under the most degraded police of any town in Europe. If any future historian may wish to search for the

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causes that have spread so turbulent a spirit among our seamen, he will find them best in these haunts of drunkenness and vice. What avail medical skill, or an investigation of remote and occasional causes of disease, while such polluted sources of destruction to health are overlooked. The injury to health in this instance is also aggravated, by a ninety gun ship's company being crammed into a hulk of sixty guns, made still more crowded by an immense number of women."

When the number of gin shops was finally reduced in Plymouth Dock from 300 to 100 "it was prophesied that I should be found murdered in the streets."

"This grievance to public service seems to have originated with some avaricious brewers or spirit-dealers and distillers, who had interest sufficient to lay hold of an immense number of public houses that obtained licences from the passive compliance of some neighbouring magistrates. A new model of getting custom was observed by the publicans, who received into their houses all the unfortunate women, to the number of some thousands. These wretches flock to the naval sea-ports for the wages of prostitution, after being debauched in the interior of the country by the idle and dissolute soldiery. Thus, the populous town of Dock was apparently converted into a huge brothel. The inhabitants themselves, eager in the pursuit of those profits which war produces, beheld with tame indifference their neighbourhood subjected as it were, to legalize prostitution; nor once thought what a dreadful example was exhibited in the face of open day, to contaminate the manners of the rising generation. The talk of magistracy, perhaps never became so ignominious, as in disannulling what itself had created: for the Duke of Portland had ordered the houses to be reduced to one hundred, so that two hundred were shut up!—The respectable part of the community acknowledged the obligations they lay under to a public officer, and a stranger, for correcting the police of their town.

"This business must be remembered as a great triumph to the naval service of the country. It has called the attention of the government to watch the proceedings of vitiated magistracy, and to protect, by wholesome regulations, a body of men, who, when from under the discipline and vigilance of their officers, are no better than inconsiderate children. Their health will by these means be preserved; they will escape the snares of the disaffected and designing, and their moral conduct will have a chance to be improved."

In 1795 a lady of fashion complained that she could not get lemons and oranges for her "large dinners to small parties" (Trotter's mild invective) because they had all been put in contribution for the navy. "It is a shame," said her Ladyship, "that the nation's money should be expended in this way. Captain P. tells me that these things are

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not good for sailors and what is worse this physician can persuade Lord Howe to anything.” On the other hand poor Trotter was boycotted by the market women of Portsmouth. They would not sell a cabbage or anything to his servant. “Your master” said they, “has spoiled our trade by sending all the *sallad* to Spithead.”

Lord St. Vincent and Trotter locked horns on the subject of flannel underwear. The worthy admiral having expert knowledge by virtue of his exalted station took it on himself to issue a general order to the captains of his ships “to inculcate this doctrine” (the importance of flannel next the skin to prevent consumption in those suffering with catarrhs, coughs, and common colds), “in the minds of their surgeons who from *caprice or perverse opposition* to every wholesome regulation grossly neglect this important duty.”

“It is plain from the nature of this order,” says Trotter, “that some accusing spirit has been at work.— From direct application of the medical officers to Earl Howe, these articles became a part of naval cloathing in the severe weather of January and February 1795. At that rigorous season Lady Howe kindly presented a suit of flannel to every man on board the Queen Charlotte. All the surgeons of whom I have made inquiry, are in the constant practice of attending to the cloathing of the sick at all times. In these pages are proofs sufficient to rescue them from the imputation of neglect. Had his Lordship inquired a little further, he would probably have learned from their officers, that they are a respectable body of professional men; faithful and humane in the discharge of their office; and earning the humble pittance which they receive from their country, with as much integrity as any class of men whatever. Men that had received a share of polite, as well as a medical education, could not but be deeply wounded with the language of this order. The very practice which his Lordship here inculcates carries with it its own confutation. Only think of the condition of a seaman at hard labour, being drenched in perspiration with flannel next his skin: he has no wardrobe to shift himself, and if he does not shift he is no better than a walking stink-pot. It will be the same if he sleeps in bed with this flannel on: the practice is filthy and unwholesome. What consumes so much perfumery in the present day it is the beau swaddled in flannel to cover the indelicate smell of his own atmosphere. If British seamen are to wear flannel next their skins, they are not subjects for a ship; they must soon lose the hardihood of constitution that fits them for their duty. Clothe them as warm as you please, but in the name of cleanliness give them linen or cotton next the skin. Read our history of phthisis, and judge whether flannel could have counteracted its causes.”

“About this time Vice Admiral Lord Nelson, complained of a violent ophthalmia in his only eye, with a membranous substance

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seemingly spreading fast over the pupil. His Lordship's flag was just hoisted in the San Josef. All persons round felt for his Lordship's indisposition, and many quack collyria were recommended and sent to him. I prescribed a dark room, and bathing the eye every hour with cold spring water, which in 24 hours had a surprising effect, and in two days more the inflammation was entirely gone. Cold spring water I have long thought the best eye-water.

"March 16th. The Admiralty have abolished the private surveys at the hospitals for consumptive cases, from representation, as they were deemed inconsistent with the spirit of naval service.

"I have also obtained a commodious decked vessel for carrying our sick from Cawsand Bay to the hospital.—The best period for obtaining favours from Ministers, is when they first come into power."

"The use of flannel next the skin has become a very general practice in phthisis; and the moment any person is phthisically disposed he is immediately recommended to wrap himself in this kind of clothing. But this custom is certainly to be followed with some qualification. To preserve the body in a grateful and equal temperature must be very desirable in this disease; but it never could be intended to keep flannel so long in contact with the human body without shifting, as we daily see done. Those who wear it sleep with it on, and must very soon become offensive. It therefore ought never to be continued beyond a single night without a change; otherwise the body will be confined as it were in a bath of impure air, that ought to be exhaled instead of being accumulated. Very frequent ablution of the whole surface should be regularly attended to during the use of flannel."

Ricord is commonly credited with having first differentiated between gonorrhoea and syphilis, establishing them as separate morbid entities, in contradistinction to the views of John Hunter and others. Undoubtedly Ricord's talent and fame were such that his announced opinions carried conviction; but Trotter's "*Medicina Nautica*" was first published two years before Ricord was born, and Trotter not only gives it as his unhesitating opinion that gonorrhoea and syphilis are distinct diseases but names Dr. Duncan, of Edinburgh, as the first person to promulgate this view. It seems remarkable that neither Lind (he speaks of a man who died "in a salivation for the pox" on the voyage from the Cape to Spithead) nor Blane had anything much to say on the subject of venereal diseases; but it is characteristic of Trotter, the earnest, thoroughgoing student and critic of men and manners, that he not only discusses this topic but makes frequent allusions to it throughout his works, and views it with lively concern. In his tabulated reports on the health of ships we find reference to venereal disease, but Blane's reports (the ones in his book, at all events) are not sullied by anything so vulgar. Trotter rejoices when at last the vicious system of charging a

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sailor for the treatment of venereal disease was done away with. Ordinarily the fee was 15 shillings, and this, in conjunction with deprivation of liberty, of grog, and tobacco while on the sick list, combined to make the sailor conceal his condition from the ship's surgeon and treat himself or resort to quacks ashore. That the surgeon should have charged for such services is not surprising, seeing that he had to supply the drugs necessary for a cure. Gradually the Government became more liberal, and finally all sick necessities were provided free. This was another matter on which our worthy doctor was always commenting.

“On the whole, there were abundant proofs at hand, for a purpose, that I had long pressed with both head and heart. I therefore resolved to address the Commander in Chief, officially, on the business. My representation of the facts were received by Earl Howe and Sir Roger Curtis, with all that warmth of approbation, which the most affectionate concern for the comfort of our seamen could dictate, and for which the transactions of this fleet bear ample testimony. His lordship thought the subject of sufficient importance to engage the attention of the Lords Commissioners of Admiralty, and laid it before them. The Board of Admiralty, after making the necessary inquiries as to the amount of the sum, in the surgeons pay, were pleased to order an immediate stop to be put to the charge, and remunerated the surgeons by an allowance of money proportioned to the complement in different rates. This alteration has been received, by the liberal and scientific part of the list, with perfect satisfaction. To those on foreign stations, it is almost clear gain, for few or no venereal complaints prevail in the ships on East and West India service. Thus terminated a perquisite, illiberal from its institution, inhuman in its practice, and impolitic from its continuance. It forms an epoch in naval improvements; for hundreds of seamen, have annually fallen victims to its effects.”

“It would be well if a safe method of treating the Recent Venereal Infection, could even be extended to the seamen; for although the abolition of the fine, for the cure, has done much in making them discover their complaints early, yet we have known a degree of modesty in some of them, independent of other considerations, prevent them from applying to the surgeon, lest their names should be handed in the sick list to the Captain. We are now told that the sale of mercurial preparations in the apothecaries shops in Portsmouth, and elsewhere, has diminished in an uncommon degree, since government remunerated the surgeon for the cure... The herd of quacks and itinerant practitioners who frequented the sea-ports, and preyed on the credulity of our men, have also taken their departure from the failure of business. It was a grievous reflection to think that a sailor often paid so high as five guineas for medicines, while the disease, in

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the mean time, was gaining ground, and for which he was obliged at last to go to an hospital.”

“I shall therefore consider Gonorrhoea, with a train of symptoms peculiar to itself, as a primary disease, and incapable of producing the Confirmed Pox: the Lues, I also think never produces Gonorrhoea.”

“If any thing can prevent venereal virus from taking effect, it must be immediate ablution of the parts; I apprehend nothing surpasses the finer soaps, and common water, which ought to be continued for some time, and repeated morning and evening.

“Now it requires some space of time for the poison to be in contact with the mouth of the sensible urethra, before it is sufficiently impressed to receive the disease : if, therefore, the matter which conveys the infection should be washed off, by soap and water, before the impression is finished, you will escape the complaint; and this is the whole secret of prevention.”

Apparently Trotter did not distinguish between chancre and chancroid. He urged the use of bluestone, and there is no question that for the latter type of sore this substance is of unequalled excellence: “I have also known a small Ulcer heal up in a week, without giving any uneasiness, or having been treated as such; and the patient was led to think that a beginning Bubo was the first symptom of the disease. On the whole, the result of my own experience is, that neither Bubo, or Lues, can be produced without preceding ulceration in the genitals, or other parts that have been in contact with the venereal virus.”

The serious blunder of Trotter’s career was his exerting himself to have a line officer appointed to conduct the affairs of naval hospitals, which were often disturbed by the dissensions between the professional staff, the steward, the agent, the nurses, and by the utter lawlessness of the patients, who regarded a hospital as a prison and were forever trying to get away. It may be that at the close of the eighteenth century a doctor or surgeon in the navy could not command the respect necessary to enforce authority, even had he been invested with it; but one is surprised that with all his independence, his ability, his grasp of the new and untried. Trotter was biased by the potent influence of environment into thinking that the management of men and things is possible only to those who bear a certain hall mark. While a physician was nominally at the head of affairs, authority was divided between him and a hospital council, and then there were the commissioners for sick and wounded in London ready to interfere or override. Certainly the experiment of putting either a port captain or a civilian at the head of a naval medical establishment could only arise through prejudices based on

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traditions. At Plymouth the consequences were always distressing, often laughable.

The first governor to arrive was received with mock state. When the hospital was full of sick and wounded from Sir John Moore's army in the Peninsula there was much insubordination, and the governor insisted that the guard should turn out and the drums beat a march whenever he went by. The sergeant, on seeking instructions, was told by a young Irish officer to play the "Rogues' March." The governor did not recognize the piece, but was delighted at the noise. Everybody else nearly died of laughter. In 1846 Sir John Richardson, the physician to Haslar, pointed out the inconveniences of the system and suggested the propriety of letting doctors conduct hospitals. Similar objections were voiced by others until in 1870, when at last the control of hospitals was ceded to medical men.

GILBERT BLANE (1749-1834) was a native of Ayrshire, Scotland, and belonged to a well-to-do merchant family. At 14 he entered Edinburgh University, where he received a classical education and then began the study of medicine. (His M. D. was from Glasgow in 1778.) he began practice in London under the most favorable auspices, highly recommended by his old teachers and having for friend and patron William Hunter, who early recommended him as medical attendant to an invalid nobleman in high favor at court and in the best society. When Sir George Rodney, in 1779, assumed command of the fleet sent to raise the siege of Gibraltar he took Blane along as his physician, but in a purely civilian capacity. During the engagements incident to the fleet's mission there was a shortage of officers, and Blane was wounded while serving as a sort of aid for Rodney to carry messages to the guns, etc. It was perhaps in return for these services that he was appointed physician to the fleet. In January, 1780, he accompanied Rodney's fleet (in an official capacity this time) when it was hurriedly dispatched to the West Indies, the principal theater of the naval war with France, Blane remaining in American waters until the conclusion of peace with the revolted colonies.

In 1783 he returned to civil life, and through the influence of Rodney and others was appointed physician to St. Thomas's Hospital, London, a post which he occupied for 12 years; and then restricted himself to private practice and such work, in an advisory capacity, as was assigned him by the Government in connection with naval and military affairs. In 1795 he became one of the two medical commissioners on the Board of Sick and Wounded Sailors, and during the seven years that he held the position was able by reason of his high standing, reputation, and general popularity to secure many enactments of great importance to the health of the service. Thus, in 1796, the use of antiscorbutics was made mandatory. It was on

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his recommendation that soap began to be regularly issued to sailors and charged against their pay; that the list of free medical supplies was greatly increased and later (1804) made to include all requisites: that a space in the fore-castle was definitely assigned as a sick berth and provided with important accessories. By these and similar innovations, suggested indeed by others but secured through Blane's influence, the health of the British navy was wonderfully improved. Thus, in 1782, when the personnel (seamen and marines) aggregated 100,000, the proportion of sick (transferred to hospital) to well men was 1 to 3.3. Thirty-one years later with a personnel of 140,000 the proportion of hospital cases was only 1 to 10.75.

Blane's career furnishes a good illustration of the value of diversified types of men in every organization. Lind and Trotter were perhaps more original, more enterprising, and the latter showed a noble readiness to suffer hardship for the "beloved navy," which by reason of disability he was forced to leave with such keen regret, but it is patent to every reader of his writing that Blane attained standing not only through his "external graces" and "artificial attractions," but because of conspicuous merit. It was owing to his influence that the labors of his predecessors and contemporaries were made available for the benefit of the sick of the service. And Blane was a deep-thinking physician and a man of solid parts and not a mere society doctor; far from it. He never lost his Scotch accent, and a parody current in his day described his countenance as "sanctified, devout, and death-like." He had not been eminently successful as a teacher when attached to St. Thomas, but he was esteemed what we would call to-day an expert in sanitation. In 1797 he visited officially the Russian fleet wintering in British ports. In 1809 he accompanied a commission sent to investigate the unusual prevalence of sickness among the troops on the island of Walcheren. His report was indorsed by the army doctors (though it was most unusual to have a civilian physician and an ex-navy one at that, passing judgment in such matters) and favorably acted on by the Government. It was for this service that he was made a baronet. Blane's study of the smallpox epidemic which developed in 1818 and seemed to discredit inoculation received Jenner's hearty approval, and was republished and circulated at the latter's expense. In 1825 we find him writing to the East India Company, and in 1832 publishing a general warning about the nature of cholera and its mode of spread. His views were indorsed by the Royal College of Surgeons, but, through the force of public opinion to the contrary, an opposite stand was adopted by one of the local boards of health. Quarantine was relaxed, and soon after Great Britain was visited by a severe epidemic of cholera. One of the victims was Blane's own wife.

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Blane was a Fellow of the Royal Societies of London, Edinburgh, and Göttingen, and member of various home and foreign scientific societies, and was physician to George IV and William IV. He died at the age of 85 at No. 8 Sackville Street, Piccadilly, after suffering for many years with pruritus senilis to such an extent that finally he was taking a drachm of solid opium in 24 hours.

Lind wrote a number of books and papers on medical and sociological topics, besides his "Observations in the Diseases of Seamen," published in 1785,^{GB1785} which has the greatest interest for us. The preface to this work contains passages illustrative of Blane's manner of expression and of his modes of thought:

"I feel greatly indebted to the surgeons for the punctuality and exactness with which they furnished these returns, and I ought not to suffer any opportunity to escape of expressing my value for this class of officers. They are perhaps more regarded in our service than in that of other nations, but it would be for the public benefit if they were still more respected and encouraged. To men of liberal education and sentiments, as surgeons ought to be and generally are, the most effectual inducements for them to enter into the service, and to do their duty when there, are flattering attentions and a certain degree of estimation in the eyes of other officers. This in its operation on liberal minds would, to a certain length, stand in place of pecuniary emolument. It is what may be called, in the words of a late eloquent writer [Burke], 'The cheap defence of nations.' Liberality of manners on the part of superiors is at the same time a more likely means of ensuring a conscientious performance of duty in this profession than strict and distant behaviour, which may, indeed, operate on the minds of those whose functions are merely mechanical; but how can it infuse that tender attention to human sufferings and that sense of duty which may induce a man entrusted with the health and lives of his fellow creatures to act his part with propriety and effect?"

"It behoves everyone who engages in a profession so important and at the same time so full of ambiguity as that of medicine to discipline his mind properly with regard to the laws of evidence and the rules of investigation, so as to draw fair inferences from facts, to avoid credulity on the one hand and scepticism on the other, both of which are equally unfriendly to the discovery and application of practical truths."

"The last impediment I shall mention to the progress of medical truth is the great difficulty of appreciating testimony. We have not only to guard against our own credulity and self-deception, but those of others. In consequence of medical practitioners not accurately distinguishing between the operations of nature and of art, drawing inferences from individual cases, and being biased by favourite

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theories, not to mention the allurements of vanity and self-interest, which it is to be hoped seldom influence the regular members of the profession, it is a melancholy truth that there is perhaps no branch of human knowledge in which there is so great a want of correctness with regard to recorded facts.”

Blane deserves special credit for emphasizing the fact that no naval organization will have any noteworthy success in health conservation so long as the subject is left to the discretion or indiscretion of individual commanders, some of whom may be zealous but ignorant, while too many are distinctly indifferent. Sanitary regulations should be based on scientific principles, drawn up by persons having special knowledge and promulgated by supreme authority for general execution. He strikes the keynote of the naval surgeon's duties in these words: “My object has been prevention as much as cure. The means of prevention are also more within our power than those of cure; for it is more in human art to remove contagion, to alter a man's food and clothing, to command what exercise he is to use and what air he is to breathe, than it is to produce any given change in the internal operations of the body. What we know concerning prevention is also more certain and satisfactory, inasmuch as it is easier to investigate the external causes that affect health, than to develop the secret springs of the animal economy.” Inasmuch as prevention depends particularly on a knowledge of the external causes of disease, he collected and arranged all the facts on the subject coming under his notice. When serving with the West Indian fleet he got the admiral to require for him a monthly sanitary report from the individual ships, so that he might be fully acquainted with the general situation, prevent overcrowding of any one hospital, and have a basis for recommendation to the commander in chief regarding diet and other measures. When the fleet was in port he visited the hospital every day. Each of the West Indian islands had a hospital of a sort, but they were often very inadequate to the demands of such an unusually large force. He made it his business to supervise them and procure what they needed through personal appeals and official representations.

Blane made suggestions to the Admiralty with a view to improving conditions along the lines laid down by Lind. His method of collecting data was followed by Trotter. They provided a statistical system for the navy. The personnel of the fleet was decimated by fever, dysentery, and scurvy. The proportion of deaths to personnel in one twelve-month period was 1 to 7 of the enlisted men. The average sick list had 1 for every 5.

The fleet had left England at Christmas, gone first to Gibraltar, and then made the run across the Atlantic. On reaching the scene

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of operations the *Montague* was in the best condition of all and so continued. This was ascribed to the practice observed on her of immediately stripping and washing every man sent from the guard ship to fill the complement. Arrived at Barbados in May the fleet put ashore 750 sick, exclusive of those from three vessels so badly crippled in battle that they could not beat to windward, and so went to St. Lucia. On Blane's suggestion the men were here provided with soft bread, fresh vegetables, and milk.

The following is given by the author as typical of the reports forwarded from the ships, but the lengthy remarks of the *Alcide's* surgeon are omitted:

State of health of His Majesty's Ship Alcide, Carlisle Bay, Barbados, June 1, 1781.
[See table in: <https://archive.org/details/unitedstatesnava14unit/page/614/mode/2up>]

But the most frequent cause of death in the fleet in American waters was dysentery, owing to the incurable ulcers of the great intestines and the added depreciation of health from scurvy and sea diet. Blane felt safe in ascribing dysentery to an infectious process, because once cured on board ship the disease did not recur, nor did the disease prevail at hospitals, where great care was taken to separate the infectious from other cases.

Speaking of overcrowding as a cause of mortality, Blane notes that the hospitals at St. Lucia and St. Christopher were but temporary establishments, intended only for urgent cases. In 1780-81 there was a death for every five and one-half patients sent to the former and one for every six sent to the latter. When a proper and regular hospital was established in the last two years of the war the mortality dropped a half. However, mortality does not depend wholly on the skill of the attendants. "Some officers are unwilling that any man should die on board of their ships for fear of dispiriting the others, and many were sent to the hospital in the most desperate stage of sickness that they might there die." The hospital at Jamaica had room for 300. During May, June, and July, 1782. there were put ashore 539 men, of whom 161 died. On the other hand, in New York, out of 825 sent ashore, only 94 died, the hospital

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having superior advantages. Fields of cabbage had been planted in the vicinity, due to the humane attention of Admiral Digby, who also had cows purchased to supply milk.

The following table shows deaths in the foreign-station hospitals for the whole war:

During whole war at hospitals at home and abroad.

[See table in: <https://archive.org/details/unitedstatesnava14unit/page/616/mode/2up>]

The deaths from disease in the fleet, both aboard and at hospitals, while Blane was fleet physician—a period of three years and three months—came to 3,200, exclusive of those due to wounds.

Blane contrasts the discipline and internal economy of British and French men-of-war, to the great disadvantage of the latter. The French never washed their decks, but let them be cumbered with lumber of every kind, not even taking down bulkheads in battle. This must have increased the mortality enormously, for splinters wrought more havoc than projectiles. Night and day, even in hot climates, their gratings were covered with tarpaulins. Their lower decks had no scuppers as outlets for water and filth. This drained into the hold as into a common sink, indescribably putrid and offensive. The common French soldiers, says Blane, were averse to throwing their dead overboard (as the English did), since their relatives desired the remains to be buried with religious service when the battle was over.⁴

On the 17 ships that came out from England during February and March, 1782, the crews enjoyed excellent health, owing to their supplies of sauerkraut, molasses, and vine. The *America* was the freest from scurvy, owing to the “extraordinary humanity” and attention of the captain who, as soon as any of the men were taken ill, allowed them wine and other refreshments from his private stores. The use of that word humanity is significant. A captain showed extraordi-

4. That most uncommon English fighter, Horatio Nelson, begged Hardy, the captain of the *Victory*, not to let him be thrown overboard, saying that if the people did not want to bury him in St. Paul's he wished his body sent to his father's parsonage. It fell to Surgeon Beatty to put the dead admiral in a hogshead of alcohol, inspect it from time to time, and perform other necessary services on the much-delayed homeward voyage

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nary humanity when he exerted himself for his sick, but the Admiralty could receive unequivocal testimony as to value of lemons and fresh vegetables in preventing scurvy, and yet allow nearly half a century to go by without compelling the use of them, in spite of the reports of men dying like sheep for lack of those simple measures. It is heartrending to think that conduct like that of the *America's* captain should be eulogized as extraordinary humanity, for it compels reflections upon how much inhumanity was abroad. Peter Parker threatened to flog any man who would not salute so much as a midshipman's coat drying on a broomstick. It is all very well for Jane⁵ to say that flogging was not so terrible an affair as we of to-day might think, but no one can read Masefield's⁶ vivid word picture of the ordeal and of other incidents of life in the royal navy without realizing that it was hell afloat; without understanding why sailors drank and drank to excess. It was their only solace.

A later visit to New York gave opportunity for the fleet to land 600 sick, the maximum available hospital accommodation. The remaining 900 being kept in their respective vessels did well, for they received meat three times a week. Thirty cases of limes captured in a prize were distributed. Spruce beer was served daily. Every man got 4 pounds of apples and one-half pound of soap every week at the public charge. The wounded and other proper cases were actually allowed to go ashore for an occasional walk. Admiral Pigot's zeal for the good of the service and his natural humanity made him listen to whatever was for the benefit of his men. (Another officer of the same name was murdered in his cabin for his extraordinary inhumanity.)

Speaking of the good health enjoyed on the *Montague* and *Royal Oak* during a long period of exposure to sickness which affected the rest of the fleet, Blane says: "A particular combination of causes is necessary to produce a disease, no single one, however powerful, being sufficient without the concurrence of others. What seemed to be wanting here was the predisposition requisite for the admission of disease into the constitution; for the ships which enjoyed this happy exemption were such as had long-established and well-regulated crews accustomed to the service and climate." He records that in 1740-41 Admiral Vernon⁷ had sent 11,000 men to hospitals, and 1 in- 7 died, besides those who succumbed aboard and in two hospital ships; but this period included the disastrous expedition to Carthage, and there were many cases of yellow fever. Vincent's force was composed of 15,000 seamen and marines. Blane gives the predisposing causes of infection as loss of blood, intoxicants, fatigue, fasting, diarrhea, grief, fear, and previous habits.

5. Jane. F. T. *The British Battle Fleet*. David D. Nickerson & Co. Boston, Mass.

6. Masefield. J. *Sea Life in Nelson's Time*. Methuen & Co., London. 1905.

<https://archive.org/details/sealifeinnelsons00maseuoft>

<https://archive.org/details/sealifeinnelsons00maserich>

7. For whom Washington named his famous estate on the Potomac. He instituted the practice of serving out liquor diluted—grog.

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Blane declared that fleets should not stay at sea more than six or seven weeks at a time on sea victualing. At least one-fourth the time should be in port. But if ships were properly supplied with antiscorbutic fruits and juices they might keep the sea for four or five months.

The fleet had much sickness during June at St. Lucia, but was in a better state than the troops ashore, who lost 50 to 55 men a week in a force of 2,000 men. The army ashore in the West Indies lost 3,035 men during 1780, or 1 in every 4 men. Sickness was considerably reduced as a result of Lord Rodney's order for "all rum stills in the neighborhood to be destroyed." For February, March, and April of 1781, 17 ships (there were no returns for 7 others) lost 44 men from fever, 48 from dysentery, and 63 from scurvy.

"After collecting the returns for each month, I made abstracts of them in tables, in one column of which the complement of each ship is set down, in order to form calculations of the comparative prevalence and mortality of different diseases at different times."

TABLE II.—*Showing the proportional sickness and mortality in relation to the whole numbers on board for 14 months.*

[See table in: <https://archive.org/details/unitedstatesnava14unit/page/618/mode/2up>]

I have omitted May because the author mentions certain details which he thinks make the figures misleading.

Returning from New York to the West Indies in November, full particulars of the disastrous hurricane of October 10 were learned. Four frigates and as many sloops of war either foundered or were wrecked and about 1,000 seamen perished.

"As ships of war must be guided by the unavoidable exigencies of service, it would be absurd to consider health only; but if this were

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to be the sole object of attention, a certain salutary medium could be pointed out in dividing the time between cruising and being in harbour; and it is proper that this should be known, that regard may be had to it, as far as may be consistent with the service.”

Speaking of tropical service, the author says: “It can not be too much inculcated on those who visit tropical countries that exercise in the sun and intemperance are most pernicious and fatal practices, and that it is in general by the one or the other that the better sort of people, particularly those newly arrived from Europe, shorten their lives.”

In discussing the mortality tables of the Haslar and Plymouth naval hospitals for a period of 25 years, Blane names several reasons for the better showing made toward the last, one being “the greater observance of cleanliness and dryness and the stricter enforcement of discipline, in consequence of the conviction now entertained by officers, of the indispensable necessity of these to the health of the men under their command; the general use of lemon juice, so judiciously and liberally allowed to ships at sea for the three last years; the late increase of encouragement to surgeons, and the operation of the regulations established and put in force by the medical board of the navy.”

“ * * * and even considering men merely as a commodity, it could be made evident, in an economical and political view, independent of moral considerations, that the lives and health of men might be preserved at much less expense and trouble than what are necessary to repair the ravages of disease.”

“Every one who has served in a great fleet must have remarked that out of ships with the same complement of men, who have been the same length of time at sea, and have been victualed and watered in the same manner, some are extremely sickly, while others are free from disease. Is it not naturally to be inferred from hence, that the health of men at sea depends in a great measure upon circumstances within the power of officers, and, indeed, upon their exertions much more than medical care ?”

“It is to be remarked, however, that exercise and temperance may be carried to excess, and that in these there is a certain salutary medium; for, when labour and abstinence amount to hardship, they are equally pernicious as indulgence and indolence. This is strongly exemplified in seamen; for, in consequence of what they undergo, they are in general short lived, and have their constitutions worn out ten years before the rest of the laborious part of mankind.”

“The most chronic complaints, which a long course of fatigue, exposure to the weather, and other hardships tend to bring on, are pulmonary consumptions, rheumatisms, and dropsies. It is also to be considered that the complaints, particularly the last, are farther

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fomented by hard drinking, which is a common vice among this class of men, and they are led to indulge in it by the rigorous and irregular course of duty incident to their mode of life.”

Passing from a minute chronicle of the incidents of the West Indies service to a discussion of certain diseases and health conditions generally. Blane proves himself a practical and thoughtful observer. He cites facts, and always reasons about them, seeking an explanation. In many instances his inferences are incorrect, but at any rate he had hit on the precise phenomena which we to-day consider significant. When he believes he is right, Blane can be emphatic; when he is in doubt he hazards an opinion, but humbly admits that he is in terra incognita.

“And in order to guard against the diseases of this climate in general it would be more proper to take some large doses of bark once in either of these periods than to make a constant practice of taking a little, as I have known some people do, by which they may also render their body in some measure insensible to its good effects.”

“There are few subjects more abstruse and difficult of investigation than this of infection.” “Why is the body incapable of being affected more than once by certain morbid poisons, and whence comes the striking and curious differences of susceptibility to infection in different individuals at the same time and of the same individual at different times ?”

The mode of transmission of typhus puzzled Blane extremely, because his observations seemed to contradict each other. He never suspected that an animal parasite might be at the bottom of it, but he clearly perceived the role of dirt and intimate contact.

“The infection of fever differs from the specific morbid poisons—first, in its not depending in all instances on the disease itself, the common source of it being the stagnated effluvia of the human body from the want of a change of linen, while there is at the same time an exclusion of fresh air. These are the circumstances which concur to produce febrile infection in jails, ill-regulated hospitals, and ill-disciplined ships. Secondly, this infection may exist about the persons of men without producing the disease. This happens to those about whose persons it was generated. Thirdly, it may be caught more than once in life.”

“It is necessary that those who direct the navy, either in a civil or military capacity, should be aware of the causes of sickness and mortality, in order to guard against them as far as is practicable. From an indolent acquiescence in this belief of the hardships, and inconveniencies of war being unavoidable, I have known neglect to arise in the conduct of officers with regard to those under their command, as if it was not the duty of a commander to employ his utmost

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attention to alleviate the misfortunes and mitigate the sufferings of his fellow-creatures; and we have seen that much more of the calamities of war arise from disease than from the sword. The like excuse might be framed for the neglect of stores and arms, which the hurry of service might equally expose to injury. We see, indeed, infinite pains taken to prevent cordage from rotting, and arms from rusting; but however precious these may be as the necessary implements of war, it will not be disputed that human hands are still more so; yet, though there is the additional inducement of humanity to watch over the health of men, I do not think that this, in general, is studied with a degree of attention equal to what is bestowed on some inanimate objects.”

Regarding immunity he says: “Infection, like some other poisons, does not so readily affect those who are accustomed to it, and therefore those who are in the habit of being exposed to it, frequently escape its bad effects, especially if it is gradually applied, as must be the case with those about whose persons it is generated. For the like reason, physicians and nurses are less susceptible than others; and strangers, who are accustomed to a pure air, are the most susceptible of any.”

He quotes some pertinent remarks from the writings of Dr. Short, and says: “It is observed by Dr. Short that contagious epidemics are more frequent and fatal in the country than in London, and this may probably be accounted for on the same principle, for every person in a great town is exposed to the breath and effluvia of others, and to a variety of putrid exhalations, which are unavoidable where multitudes inhabit together, but they are so used to them that they are not affected by them, whereas in the country, where people are less accustomed to each other’s company and less used to impure air in general, they are the more readily affected when infection is introduced among them. It may even admit of a doubt if any society of men living together are entirely free from morbid contagion. It certainly sometimes happens that a ship with a long-established crew shall be very healthy, yet if strangers are introduced among them who are also healthy sickness will be mutually produced.”

In contrast to Trotter, he admits the evils of impressment, but seems to regard this measure as a necessary one, or at least so firmly established that no criticism is permissible. “The mode of manning the navy by pressing, I take it for granted, is unavoidable; at any rate it would not become me to arraign a practice which has had the public sanction for ages. It is, however, one of the principal means both of generating and spreading the seeds of disease, in consequence of the indiscriminate seizure of men for the public

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service and the confinement⁸ that is necessary to secure them. And as the exigencies of the service make it necessary to admit persons of every description, there is no other remedy for this evil but to annihilate, if possible, the contagion that may thus be conveyed into ships of war.”

“Among brute animals, as well as the human species, acute infectious distempers are generated by their being confined together in numbers, in all-ventilated places. A complaint of this kind is common in dog kennels, and also among sheep, where they are housed during the winter, or when too much crowded on board of ships. The glanders in horses is little known but in large stables, where the air is not freely admitted. Birds in aviaries are also subject to a peculiar disease.”

“It may be farther remarked in favour of cleanliness, that it is not only directly conducive to health, but is naturally connected with habits of good order, sobriety, and other virtues. The most cleanly men are always the most decent and honest, and the most slovenly and dirty are the most vicious and irregular.

“Officers might be very useful in making an early discovery of complaints, by observing those who droop and look ill in the course of duty; for seamen think it unmanly to complain, and have an aversion to be put on the sick list. I have heard of a method practiced in some ships, of keeping a book on the quarter deck for the officer to mark the names of such men as might look ill, or might be missed from duty upon calling the roll, in order to afford the surgeon a means of finding out those who should be the objects of his care.

“Those whose profession it is to superintend the health of the ship, would find it for their ease and interest, and should consider it as their duty, to walk over the different decks once a day, or every other day, in order to make an early discovery of those who may be taken ill.”

“Should any officer object to the trouble and inconvenience of all this, let him reflect for a moment how much more troublesome and inconvenient, as well as noisome and disagreeable, sickness itself proves to be; let him reflect that the efficiency of the ship, considered as a bulwark of defence, or an engine of annoyance, depends on the number of healthy hands, and that his own character is to depend on the exertions to be made by them in the day of battle, not to mention the attention due from him as a man to the sufferings of the objects themselves.”

“The great attention that has of late been paid to dryness by officers of the navy seems to be one of the principal causes of the superior

8. Enlisted men rarely got liberty during the progress of a war because those who had been impressed would seize the opportunity to desert.

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health which at present prevails in our ships of war. One of the methods lately practised for producing dryness has been to rub the decks with sand heated in the oven.”

Blane gave serious attention to the diet of the well and the sick afloat and ashore, and made recommendations which were in part adopted and laid down in instructions drawn up by the Admiralty in 1796 for the guidance of navy surgeons. Unfortunately, the provisions for enlarging and varying the diet of the sick were soon abrogated, and our author deplors the necessity of having to depend on the generosity of the officers. “This practice is highly honourable to the character of our sea officers; but anything dependent on the casual bounty of individuals is too precarious a provision in such an important point of service.”

Blane made a number of experiments in preserving foods, and found that beef could be cured with but half the usual amount of salt by using hydrochloric acid, pimento, and juniper berries; but, as he remarks in another paragraph, it is not the salt that gives scurvy, but a deficiency of other things in the diet. He reiterates his recommendation for more issue of fresh bread, insisting that it would be easy and economical to do so, and citing the example of the French ships.

Table exhibiting the daily allowance of provisions for each man in the navy.

[See table in: <https://archive.org/details/unitedstatesnava14unit/page/622/mode/2up>]

“This has continued from the last century till the alterations above mentioned, all of which, except the introduction of vinegar, currants, and raisins, have been made in the three last years of the war which ended in 1783. When the stock of small beer is exhausted, half a pint of spirits is allowed daily, diluted with four or five times its quantity of water. When wine is supplied, the daily allowance of it to a man is one pint. Other exchanges are usual on foreign voyages, such as three pounds of flour and half a pound of raisins, or half a pound of currants, or half a pound of beef suet pickled, in lieu of a four-pound piece of beef, or a two-pound piece of pork, with pease. Half a pound of rice is allowed for a pint of oatmeal.”

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“Though it has been my object to introduce as many articles of diet as possible, independent of salt provisions, it does not follow that these are in themselves unwholesome. They are pernicious by being made almost the sole and exclusive article; but if used in moderate quantity, they are even in some respects well adapted for the food of seamen.”

He wisely remarks: “It does not appear that it is the salt quality alone of the provisions used at sea that makes them productive of scurvy, but also the want of their native juices and of the nutritious principle.”

“The large utensils employed to boil the provisions are made of copper, and it sometimes happens from neglect that these are allowed to contract a rust, which is one of the most active poisons we know. The neglect consists chiefly in allowing anything acid, or what is liable to become acid, such as gruel or burgoo, to remain for a length of time without being washed out; for when victuals have been prepared in the boilers thus uncleaned, they produce the most violent effects, even to the loss of life, as once happened in a ship belonging to our fleet.”

Blane discusses the importance of pure drinking water and how to obtain it, and gives details for its aeration, ascribing full credit to Lind for his contributions to the subject. He tells of the value of quicklime, and how it will destroy algae and small insects.

Of clothing, “the most artificial circumstance in the life of man,” he writes at length and subscribes to Lind’s advice about uniforms for the crew. He notes the efficacy of hydrotherapy in the treatment of delirium, and urges that when sweating is indicated it be brought about by proper sudorific drugs and not by piling on bedclothes and shutting out the air. Every naval hospital should have facilities for giving warm baths at short notice. Blane is inclined to doubt the advisability of cold baths and affusions in fevers. The matter is one for observation and reflection. It may be “a valuable remedy or only one of those to which novelty and fashion give a temporary currency.” With proper impartiality he cites the success which attended this practice in the hands of a certain physician of the West Indies, who used the cold bath in a number of cases with such prompt relief of symptoms that the patients themselves called for it day and night. On the other hand there was the case of a girl with smallpox who bathed in a brook and died !

“The good effects resulting from the indulgent treatment of men are, that it encourages them to enter into the service, and to do their duty with cheerfulness and resolution. There is something more daunting to the mind of man to see his companions suffering under oppression and languishing in disease, or perishing miserably from sores or sickness, than in the terrors of fire and sword, which,

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as we have seen, make the least part of the calamities of war. The good treatment of seamen, in so far as it regards their health, is by no means incompatible with strict discipline. Indeed strictness and even severity is necessary with seamen; for it is observed with regard to men who are used to arbitrary government, that they can not bear indulgence and relaxation. But the steady enforcement of discipline and regularity is so far from being akin to cruelty, that it tends to prevent not only sickness but the commission of crimes, and consequently rendering the infliction of punishment less frequent and necessary. The chief excellence in the character of an officer seems to consist in uniting strict discipline with indulgence and humanity.”

Part II concludes with words of profound wisdom, as appropriate now as in the days of the broad-minded man who penned them: “The subject of the preceding remarks has been the prevention of disease, and it has appeared that the means of this are not so much in the province of the medical profession as of those who are entrusted with the direction of the navy in a civil or military capacity, and that with regard to cure and recovery also a great deal depends upon them, by their having it in their power to make a suitable provision of proper diet and cordials. The great importance of the subject will plead my excuse for again calling to mind that such attentions are not only dictated by humanity, but would be the greatest wisdom in an economical and national light, considering how expensive it is to *replace* men and to support invalids, not to mention that it is upon the health and lives of men that every public exertion essentially depends, and upon which may depend not only the character of officers but the national character and safety on the day of battle.”

“There is no situation of life in which there is room for more virtues, more conduct and address, than that of a sea officer. The men are thrown upon his humanity and attention in more views than one: they are subject to a more arbitrary exertion of power than the constitution of the state authorizes in civil life. It is the character of the seamen to be thoughtless and neglectful of their own interest and welfare, requiring to be tended like children; but from their bravery, utility, and other good qualities they seem entitled to a degree of *parental* tenderness and attention from the state they protect and the officers they obey.”

It will not be amiss to devote a few lines to Blane’s therapy, noting particularly the points in which it approximates in some measure to our own. Opium in dysentery is to be used with great caution and only in certain stages or combined with starch in soothing enemata for tenesmus. Ipecac in doses of a grain or two and salines are to be preferred. When the stomach will not tolerate Peruvian bark it may be administered per rectum; and arsenic is a valuable adjuvant in

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treatment of intermittent and remittent fevers. Warm baths are highly commended for a variety of purposes. In many cases of illness diet is of more value than drugs; likewise fresh air, nursing, and general regimen. Blisters are often of great service in certain fevers. Do not remove the scarf skin. To do so delays healing and causes subsequent discomfort to the patient. Rectal feeding can be successfully practiced. He cautions against zeal in bleeding and purging in fevers. Mild measures are preferable—sudorifics and enemata. Diarrheas induced by medication may be fatal, but an apparent diarrhea from irritation due to scybala calls for an evacuant from above.

Opium must be given with consideration of pulse and circulation. In some it does not bring the desired ease and quiet, but excitement. Its good effects are often best brought out by using it in combination with other drugs. Blane shows himself in treatment an eminently conservative and thoughtful physician.

A very interesting chapter is that treating of wounds in action and their results. In the naval actions of the fleet in April, 1782, the wounded aggregated 810. Of these 354 died—266 outright, 67 on board their ships, and 21 at hospitals. Seventeen of the deaths were due to tetanus—a very common complication. The small number of deaths at hospitals was due to delay in transferring patients. Treatment of tetanus was almost uniformly unsuccessful, whether amputation when symptoms developed, salivation by mercury combined with opium, or opium and hot baths were resorted to. The last named measure occasionally succeeded.

“There is a singular species of accident to which engagements at sea are liable, called, perhaps improperly, the wind of a ball. In whatever manner it is accounted for, it is a fact that a part is sometimes severely hurt, and even life destroyed, without any visible external injury or breach of the parts, nor any appearance of the body from whence the injury proceeded. This is a fact which does not admit of doubt, but the manner in which the effect is here produced is a matter of conjecture. It is perhaps owing to the compression and tremor of the air in consequence of its resistance to the motion of the ball.” [One is reminded by these observations of the accounts of so-called shell shock in the early period of the World War.]

“The class of wounds most peculiar to a sea engagement are scorches from the accidental explosion of gunpowder, and in most of the campaigns in which I have served they have been very frequent and fatal.

“In the battles of 1780 and 1781, one-fourth part of the whole killed and wounded was from this sort of accident; but on the 9th and 12th of April, 1782, only two accidental explosions of gunpowder happened in the whole fleet, by one of which one life was

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lost; by the other, two. This difference was owing partly to greater experience and habits of caution acquired in the course of the war, and partly to certain improved methods in working the artillery introduced by Sir Charles Douglas; these consisted, 1st, in wetting the wads, which prevents their inflaming and blowing back when in battle the weather side of the ship is engaged; a circumstance which, without this precaution, gives occasion to a number of accidents, by the burning parts catching the loose powder, or setting fire to the cartridges. 2dly, in the use of goosequill tubes and small priming boxes, made of tin, instead of the large horns formerly in use, whereby great quantities of powder were scattered about and exposed to accidental fire. 3dly, in the use of locks, which was practised with great success in several ships, and was found to make the operation both more safe and more expeditious." When locks were first introduced the prejudice against them was strong, but in the battle of the Nile a ship whose guns were provided with the device was so superior in marksmanship as to afford a convincing argument in its favor.

With the modesty becoming to a man who professed himself no surgeon, Blane brings up the mooted question of whether amputation should be performed immediately or later. He quotes Dr. William Hunter's statement that "men whose strength has been impaired by the confinement and long suffering from an injury survive amputation more frequently than those who undergo it in the height of their health and strength after an injury"; but adds two cogent reasons why a sailor might with advantage be operated on at once: The motion of a ship renders the management of fractures difficult; the constitution of sailors by their manner of life is at all times approximated to the state which Hunter considered favorable to amputation.

In general close action, which the British commanders loved because it permitted the fighting qualities of the individual to come into play, was productive of fewer mortal wounds than fighting at long range. At close range the velocity of cannon balls was so great that they perforated the ship's sides without splintering the timbers. "A quick-flying ball makes an aperture smaller than its own diameter, whereas a spent one produces innumerable deadly splinters, at the same time shivering the object it strikes.

"It frequently happens that men bleed to death before assistance can be procured, or lose so much blood as not to be able to go through an operation. In order to prevent this it has been proposed, and on some occasions practiced, to make each man carry about him a garter, or piece of rope yarn, in order to bind up a limb in case of profuse bleeding. If it should be objected that this, from its solemnity, may

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be apt to intimidate common men, officers at least should make use of some such precaution, especially as many of them, and those of the highest rank, are stationed on the quarter deck, which is one of the most exposed situations, and far removed from the cockpit, where the surgeon and his assistants are placed.”

Toward the close of the book there is a chapter that to-day would be designated “On first aid.” Then come several score prescriptions in Latin, among them treatments for gonorrhoea and malign ulcers.

In the concluding pages is found a very illuminating letter to Rufus King, “Minister Plenipotentiary from the States of America to the Court of London,” dated November 26, 1798, which begins thus:

“SIR: I sit down to perform the promise I made you this morning, of putting on paper some remarks on the nature of the yellow fever and the means of preventing it.

“In doing this I shall chiefly confine myself to those views of it in which the magistrate is concerned. The adopting of measures for the prevention of disease is one of the most important duties of a wise and patriotic Government, and the discovery of these means, as well as the efficiency of the steps to be taken, must depend on a thorough knowledge of the causes by which it is excited and influenced.”

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